

D1.2 Multiparty Computation Schemes to Support Homomorphic Encryption, Functional Encryption and Differential Privacy

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3 Status, Change History and Glossary

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Table 1 – Status Change History

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0.3	05.02.2025	22	TUNI	Added remaining background
0.4	12.02.2025	37	TUNI	Added FE[r]Chain
0.5	17.02.2025	50	TUNI	Added FE/HE Tranciphering
0.6	21.02.2025	57	TUNI	Added Related Work Analysis
0.7	25.02.2025	63	TUNI	Added Function Secret Sharing
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0.9	03.03.2025	73	TUNI	Internal Review Version Ready
1.0	28.03.2024	73	TUNI&RISE	Internal Comments Addressed and Final Version Ready

Table 2 – Deliverable Change History

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

HE	Homomorphic Encryption
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
LHE	Levelled Homomorphic Encryption
SHE	Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption
HHE	Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption
FE	Functional Encryption
MIFE	Multi-Input Functional Encryption
MCFE	Multi-Client Functional Encryption
IPFE	Inner-Product Functional Encryption
MPC	Multi-Party Computation
n PC	n -Party Computation
FSS	Function Secret Sharing
PRNG	Pseudo Random Number Generator
CW	Correction Word
pk	Public Key
sk	Secret Key
evk	Evaluation Key
dk	Decryption Key
mpk	Master Public Key
msk	Master Secret Key
ADV	Adversary
IND-CPA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack
IND-CCA	Indistinguishability under Chosen Ciphertext Attack
EU-F-CMA	Existential Unforgeability under Chosen Message Attack
ADV	Adversary
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography
PKE	Public Key Encryption
SKE	Symmetric Key Encryption

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CSP	Cloud Service Provider
(D)O	(Data) Owner
(D)A	(Data) Analyst
KC	Key Curator
U	Users
PPT	Probabilistic Polynomial Time
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
DP	Differential Privacy

Table 3 – List of abbreviations and acronyms

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Executive Summary

The goal of the HARPOCRATES project is to bridge the gap between research of modern cryptographic techniques, which allow operations on encrypted data, and their implementation in real world scenarios. The prior deliverable for Work Package 1 (D1.1 Homomorphic Encryption, Functional Encryption and Function Hiding) focused on developing and applying novel Functional Encryption (FE), Homomorphic Encryption (HE) and Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption (HHE) schemes for the project. In this deliverable (D1.2 Multiparty Computation Schemes to Support Homomorphic Encryption, Functional Encryption and Differential Privacy) we show solutions to expand our previously developed works through the use of Multi-Party Computation (MPC) and address an important concern of verifiability through Zero Knowledge Proofs (ZKP). Throughout this document we introduce all required backgrounds for understanding our constructions and those seen in other literature, as well as document our constructions with the aforementioned techniques. The contents of this deliverable can be summarised as such:

- In accordance to the Multiparty Computation Schemes to Support HE and FE task, we develop ways to expand FE constructions to allow for multi-input and multi-client applications, where the generated decryption key and in turn the decryption from the key can be verified to be correct without affecting the security of the FE scheme
- We construct a transciphering HE/FE scheme, which allows seamless switching from a lattice-based FE scheme to an equivalent HE scheme allowing us to make use of both the benefits of FE as well as the benefits of HE. This construction also allows us to remove one of the biggest drawbacks of FE, namely its requirement for a trusted third party.
- Following the task of Differential Privacy with Cryptography, we define DP and provide a mathematical DP construction, which can be applied to our transciphering HE/FE method to further increase its security against novel threats without substantially affecting the usability of the scheme.
- Additionally, we analysed existing literature, which makes use of MPC in the scenario of Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML), we explore the current trends in the field and assess its current state. We document our findings and key takeaways of the field including the advantages and disadvantages of it.
- We explore Function Secret Sharing (FSS), a novel paradigm in MPC, by analysing its use in a ML application and show areas for improvements in the paradigm, which we explore throughout the project and document in Work Package 2.

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4 Introduction

From Caesar's cipher to post-quantum primitives, cryptography evolved in many civilizations and has been used in countless scenarios to solve numerous problems, from war tactics to online payments. With the technology currently at our disposal and the development of the internet, one could pertain that cryptography is at its peak when it comes to privacy matters. Though research has provided many answers in the past dozen years, every answer raises even more questions. Since the multiple breakthroughs in Public-Key Encryption (PKE) [1, 2, 3], a new need has unfolded in cryptography, namely the need to continue using encrypted data. This need raised a variety of novel research directions, including Homomorphic Encryption (HE) [4, 5, 6, 7], Functional Encryption (FE) [8, 9, 10] and Multi-Party Computation (MPC) [11, 12, 13] as well as its paradigms like Function Secret Sharing (FSS) [14, 15, 16]. Through these modern cryptographic techniques, encrypted data remains functional and analysable for online services, while still maintaining the privacy of the user. However, despite the progress made in research, its adoption has remained stagnant.

Through the HARPOCRATES project we aim to reduce this gap between theoretical research and practical adoption of these technologies in industry, healthcare and governments. In deliverable D1.1 of this project we introduced multiple FE and (Hybrid) HE-based schemes, which could be actively used in different usecases. In this document, we expand the functionality of HE and FE through homomorphic transciphering and explore the capabilities of MPC techniques for performing operations in a secure manner.

4.1 Privacy & Trust in Functional Encryption

As we have seen in many different contexts, privacy is a large and very nebulous target that is hard to approach directly. This challenge extends to FE, where, despite the remarkable capabilities of the schemes, there is a fundamental issue hiding beneath its surface. More precisely, as in many cryptographic schemes and cryptosystems, there is the need for a trusted entity – one of the big hurdles that cryptographers have wrestled with for decades.

Before we elaborate on the actual privacy and trust issues that cryptographers are grappling with in FE, let us first describe a typical application scenario. In a classic FE scenario, there are three entities: the users, the curator and the analyst. A user is generating data, encrypts it and sends it to the cloud where it is stored. Later, the analyst wishes to compute a specific function f over a set of ciphertexts stored in the cloud. To do so, contacts the curator and asks him to generate a decryption key specifically for the function f she wishes to run over the data. Upon reception of the request, the curator generates the functional decryption key dk_f and sends it to the analyst. Using this key, the analyst can compute the function f over the encrypted data

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and get the final result as if data were unencrypted but without getting access to any of the individual values (only to the final result).

The above scenario poses two main privacy issues:

- P1.** The level of trust is placed in the curator may be unrealistic. This is because, the curator can generate a decryption key for any function and any set of ciphertexts, hence making it a master entity that can eventually decrypt all data and breach user privacy at will. To the best of our knowledge, this is a problem that exists in *all* currently published FE schemes involving a key curator.
- P2.** We identified that FE schemes naturally suffer from the important, till now overlooked, problem of *function-privacy* (or function-hiding). That is, ensuring that a curator who is performing a functional decryption generation will output the correct result *without* learning anything about the computed function. In other words, when the curator receives a request from an analyst asking to get a functional decryption for a function f , the curator should process this in a blind way. This means that:
 - (a) The curator must be able to generate a correct dk_f in a blind way (i.e. without knowing that this key corresponds to function f).
 - (b) If, at a later point, the curator receives another request asking to generate again a functional decryption key for the same function f , they should not be able to determine that these two requests correspond to the same function.

4.2 Contributions

The core contributions covered in this document can be summarized as follows:

- C1.** We endow the FE protocol of Castagnos *et al.* [17] with a *multi-client* feature. This new construction aims at allowing the users and the key curator a better management of the ciphertexts accessible by the analyst.
- C2.** Our construction includes a *verification* method to ensure the correctness of the computation the analyst receives. Additionally, we provide a variant to extend the protocol to n users, encrypting their data separately.
- C3.** We redefine the landscape of the FE field by introducing a completely new perspective. We develop a method to homomorphically evaluate the FE algorithms, thus laying the foundation for a transciphering technique between HE and FE.
- C4.** We show how this HE-FE transciphering can be used to create applications where no trusted entity is required. Hence, our construction provides a realistic solution to the long-standing issue of trusted entities, which has been bubbling under many of the existing FE schemes.

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- C5.** We present CaTT, a use-case protocol relying on the transciphering technique, showing its applicability in realistic scenarios. CaTT relies on a model of trust that does *not* require a trusted authority, presenting a strong alternative to existing Multi-Party Computation (MPC) techniques. We hope that this work will kick-start a period of greater trust and sustained research in the field of FE.
- C6.** We analyse various aspects of the implementations of current Machine Learning (ML) and Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML) solutions, such as security, computational complexity, and adversarial models to get an overview of current SotA implementations. We also highlight the importance of Open-Source Implementations (OSI) in research. By encouraging researchers to prioritize OSI, we aim to bridge the gap between theoretical advancements and real-world applications. This promotes improved reproducibility, wider adoption and impact, and long-term sustainability in the field of PPML.
- C7.** Additionally, in our analysis of current literature we explore an article which makes use of Function Secret Sharing (FSS), a novel paradigm in MPC, which allows additively sharing a function in a way that the function remains secret, but its functionality remains. We test FSS in a PPML application and analyse areas for improvements by measuring the training time and communication costs.

4.3 Organisation

This document is organised into the following five sections. Firstly, [section 5](#) provides the core background to understand the constructions by providing the notation, mathematical background and definitions used throughout the document. Secondly, [section 6](#) covers FE[r]chain, which provides a verifiable multi-party and multi-input FE construction. Thirdly, [section 7](#) explains how HE can be used to remove the trusted authority in FE through homomorphic transciphering. Lastly, [section 8](#) analyses related literature in the field of HE with Differential Privacy (DP), Multi-Party HE (MHE) and MPC, specifically for PPML application. From this we identified FSS and further explored it in [subsection 8.6](#) to discover the advantages and disadvantages of the technique in PPML applications. Our findings and constructions are concluded in [section 9](#).

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5 Background

This section provides the necessary mathematical background and definitions for understanding the contents of the deliverable. Firstly, we define the notation we use throughout the deliverable and provide a definition for Public-Key Encryption schemes.

Notation: For $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $[n]$ is the set $\{1, \dots, n\}$. Vectors are written in bold lowercase letters, and ones denotes $\langle \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \rangle = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i$ the inner product of two vectors $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ and $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_n)$. For a set \mathcal{Y} , one uses $x \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \mathcal{Y}$ if x is sampled at random from \mathcal{Y} . Generally, we write $x \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \chi(\mathcal{Y})$ if x is sampled from \mathcal{Y} following a distribution χ . The image of a function $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$ is denoted $\text{Im}(f) \subseteq \mathcal{Y}$. The probability of an event $A \in \Omega$ is denoted $\mathbb{P}(A)$, where $\mathbb{P} : \Omega \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a probability measure on a set Ω usually omitted for brevity. A (probabilistic) polynomial time algorithm \mathcal{A} , or (P)PT, is a (randomized) algorithm for which there exists a polynomial $P(x)$ s.t. for all input x , the running time of $\mathcal{A}(x)$ is bounded by $|P(x)|$. A function $f : \mathbb{N} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is said negligible if $\forall \delta \in \mathbb{N}, \exists x_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall x \geq x_0, f(x) < x^{-\delta}$. One denotes $\text{negl}(\cdot)$ an arbitrary negligible function.

Definition 1 (Public-Key Encryption (PKE)). A *Public-Key Encryption scheme* for message space \mathcal{M} and ciphertext space \mathcal{C} consists of three polynomial time algorithms KGen , Enc , Dec defined as follows:

- $\text{KGen}(1^\lambda)$. The key generation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a security parameter λ , it outputs a pair of keys (sk, pk) , respectively the secret and public keys;
- $\text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m)$. The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a public key pk and a message m in the message space \mathcal{M} , it outputs a ciphertext c in the ciphertext space \mathcal{C} . One also writes $c \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$;
- $\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, c)$. The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm. On the input of a secret key sk and a ciphertext c , it outputs a message m . One also writes $\text{Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c) \rightarrow m$.

Correctness: For the entire set of parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{KGen}(1^\lambda)$ and ciphertext $c \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$, $\mathbb{P}[\text{Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c) \neq m] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$.

The security of a PKE scheme relies on the fact that the encryption algorithm Enc is probabilistic. For well-chosen parameters, it is unlikely for two ciphertexts $c \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$ and $c' \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$ of the same plaintext to be equal. However, these are both valid encryptions of m and hence can be correctly decrypted. We call the set of such ciphertexts the *image* of

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$\text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$ and denote it as $\text{Im}(\text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m))$. More formally,

$$\text{Im}(\text{Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)) = \{c \in \mathcal{C} \mid \text{Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c) = m\}$$

5.1 Homomorphic Encryption

Definition 2 (Homomorphic Encryption). *A Homomorphic Encryption scheme HE for message space \mathcal{M}_{HE} , ciphertext space \mathcal{C}_{HE} and class of functions $\mathcal{F}_{\text{HE}} : \mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, consists of four polynomial time algorithms HE.KGen, HE.Enc, HE.Eval, HE.Dec defined as follows:*

- HE.KGen (1^λ) . *The key generation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a security parameter λ , it outputs a tuple of keys $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk})$, respectively the secret, public and evaluation keys;*
- HE.Enc (pk, m) . *The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a public key pk and a message m in the message space \mathcal{M}_{HE} , it outputs a ciphertext c in the ciphertext space \mathcal{C}_{HE} . One also writes $c \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m)$;*
- HE.Eval $(\text{evk}, f, (c_1, \dots, c_n))$. *The evaluation algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that, on input the evaluation key evk , a function $f \in \mathcal{F}_{\text{HE}}$ and n ciphertexts c_1, \dots, c_n , outputs a unique ciphertext c . One can also write $\text{HE.Eval}_{\text{evk}}(f, (c_1, \dots, c_n)) \rightarrow c$;*
- HE.Dec (sk, c) . *The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that, on input the secret key sk and a ciphertext c , outputs a message m . One also writes $\text{HE.Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c) \rightarrow m$.*

Correctness: *For all parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$, $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.KGen}(1^\lambda)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}_{\text{HE}}$ and ciphertexts $c_i \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(m_i)$, $m_i \in \mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}$, $i \in [n]$,*

$$\mathbb{P}[\text{HE.Dec}_{\text{sk}}(\text{HE.Eval}_{\text{evk}}(f, (c_1, \dots, c_n))) \neq f(m_1, \dots, m_n)] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

Remark (Evaluation Algorithm). The name *homomorphic* encryption comes from the notion of *group homomorphism*, widely used in mathematics. In an HE scheme, the encryption algorithm is indeed a group homomorphism between the group \mathcal{M}_{HE} and the group \mathcal{C}_{HE} , with their respective operations. The particularity of a homomorphism is that it preserves these operations. More precisely, an operation in \mathcal{C}_{HE} is associated to an operation in \mathcal{M}_{HE} . This is what the evaluation algorithm is: $\text{HE.Eval}_{\text{evk}}(f, \cdot)$ is the corresponding function operating on $\mathcal{C}_{\text{HE}}^n$ to a function $f(\cdot)$ that operates on $\mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}^n$. Informally, $\text{HE.Eval}_{\text{evk}}(f, (c_1, \dots, c_n)) = \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(f(m_1, \dots, m_n))$. As the function $f : \mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{M}_{\text{HE}}$ returns a single plaintext $m = f(m_1, \dots, m_n)$, the corresponding function returns a single ciphertext $c = \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(f(m_1, \dots, m_n))$ that can be decrypted using the decryption algorithm $\text{HE.Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c)$ to retrieve $m = f(m_1, \dots, m_n)$.

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5.2 Functional Encryption

Definition 3 (Functional Encryption). A functional encryption scheme FE for message space FE and class of functions \mathcal{F}_{FE} , consists of four PT algorithms FE.Setup, FE.KDer, FE.Enc, FE.Dec defined as follows:

- FE.Setup (1^λ). The setup algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a security parameter λ it outputs a (master) secret key msk and a (master) public key mpk;
- FE.Enc (mpk, m). The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of public key mpk and a message m in the message space \mathcal{M}_{FE} , it outputs a ciphertext c . One also writes $c \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{FE.Enc}_{\text{mpk}}(m)$;
- FE.KDer (msk, f). The key derivation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of the secret key msk and a function $f \in \mathcal{F}_{FE}$, it outputs a decryption key dk_f . One also writes $\text{dk}_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{FE.KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f)$;
- FE.Dec (dk_f, c); The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that, on the input of a decryption key dk_f and a ciphertext c , it outputs a message m . One also writes $\text{FE.Dec}(\text{dk}_f, c) \rightarrow m$.

Correctness: For all set of parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{FE.Setup}(1^\lambda)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}_{FE}$, $\text{dk}_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{FE.KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f)$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}_{FE}$,

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\text{FE.Dec}_{\text{dk}_f}(\text{FE.Enc}_{\text{mpk}}(m)) \neq f(m) \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

Remark (Functional Decryption Algorithm). Unlike traditional encryption schemes, the decryption algorithm does not necessarily output an element of the plaintext space, but the result of a function that takes value into an arbitrary space. This is one of the advantages of FE over HE, since the later exclusively supports the function defined onto the message space.

5.3 Semantic Security

While the security of PKE is well-studied, it is still very hard to define a universal security definition for HE and FE. The reason is two-fold: firstly, the capacity to make computations on the ciphertexts clearly impact the notion of *indistinguishability*. This is particularly true in FE, where the decryption algorithm acts as a *trapdoor*, hence challenging traditional security definitions. Secondly, the application case and the system model considered significantly impact the security expectations. If these concerns are usually delegated to the security of the protocol, the large panel of use-cases offered by both HE and FE requires the user to ask what oracle can be reasonably provided to an attacker, even at the scheme's semantic security level. A good

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example of this problem is the recent introduction by Li and Micciancio [18] of IND-CPA^D. In short, it consists in providing the attacker a conditional access to the decryption oracle. This seems like a reasonable assumption, since HE can provide the decryption of particular results to a non fully-trusted entity. However, there is yet no consensus on this level of security [19, 20], which is highly impacted by the considered use-case.

This deliverable focuses on the standard IND-CPA security, which allows a systematic reduction of the security of the HE and FE schemes to the security of our constructions.

FE Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack: This security notion is usually formalized through a security game. The game starts with a challenger flipping a truly random coin $\beta \in \{0, 1\}$, generating the master secret and public keys, and sending the master public key to the adversary \mathcal{ADV} . The latter subsequently requests functional decryption keys for functions of its choice. At some point, \mathcal{ADV} outputs two messages m_0, m_1 to the challenger, which replies with c_β . The scheme is IND-FE-CPA secure if \mathcal{ADV} cannot guess the value of β with probability greater than $1/2 + \text{negl}$. More formally, the security game is described below:

Definition 4 (IND-CPA Security for FE (IND-FE-CPA)). *We say that an FE scheme FE is IND-FE-CPA secure, if for all PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} , it holds that the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} :*

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{FE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(1^\lambda) = \left| \mathbb{P} \left[\text{Exp}_{\text{FE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(1^\lambda) \rightarrow \text{true} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \right|$$

is negligible in λ , where the experiment is defined as follows in [Figure 1](#).

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{Exp}_{\text{FE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(1^\lambda)} : \\ & \beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}; L_K, L_M \leftarrow \emptyset \\ & (\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda) \\ & \beta' \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{ADV}(1^\lambda, \text{mpk} : \mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-FE}}) \\ & \text{Return } (\beta = \beta') \end{aligned}$$

The game keeps record of the queries made by \mathcal{ADV} through a list L_M storing encryption queries and a list L_F storing functional queries. Each request is made under the condition that $f_0(m_0) = f_1(m_1)$, for any $(f_0, f_1) \in L_F$ and $(m_0, m_1) \in L_M$. This condition is mandatory, as violating it gives \mathcal{ADV} an overwhelming advantage to distinguish $f_0(m_0)$ from $f_1(m_1)$.

HE Indistinguishability under Chosen Plaintext Attack: The security notion of IND-HE-CPA security is usually formalized through a security game. The game starts with a challenger \mathcal{C} flipping a truly random coin $\beta \in \{0, 1\}$, generating the public, secret and evaluation keys, and sending the public key to the adversary \mathcal{ADV} . The latter has access to an encryption oracle, that on the input of two messages m_0, m_1 outputs the ciphertext c_β . Subsequently, \mathcal{ADV}

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<i>Oracles</i> $\mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-FE}}$	
<u>ENCRYPT</u> (mpk, m_0, m_1) If $m_0, m_1 \notin \mathcal{M}$: return \perp If $\exists (f_0, f_1) \in L_F ; f_0(m_0) \neq f_1(m_1)$: return \perp $c_\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Enc}(\text{mpk}, m_\beta)$ $L_M \leftarrow L_M \cup \{(m_0, m_1, c_\beta)\}$ return c_β	<u>KEYDER</u> (f_0, f_1) If $f_0, f_1 \notin \mathcal{F}$: return \perp If $\exists (m_0, m_1) \in L_M ; f_0(m_0) \neq f_1(m_1)$: return \perp $\text{dk}_{f_\beta} \xleftarrow{\$} \text{KDer}(\text{msk}, f_\beta, D)$ $L_F \leftarrow L_F \cup \{(f_0, f_1, \text{dk}_{f_\beta})\}$ return dk_{f_β}

Figure 1 – Oracles in the IND-FE-CPA game for an FE scheme FE and PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} : the encryption oracle ENCRYPT and the key derivation oracle KEYDER.

requests evaluations for functions of its choice. At some point, \mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess β' on the value of β . The scheme is IND-HE-CPA secure if \mathcal{ADV} cannot guess the value of β with probability greater than $1/2 + \text{negl}$. More formally, the security game is described below:

Definition 5 (IND-CPA Security for HE (IND-HE-CPA)). *Let HE = (KGen, Enc, Eval, Dec) be an HE scheme for message space \mathcal{M} and functionality space $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{M}^n \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$. We say that HE is IND-HE-CPA secure if for all PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} , it holds that the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} given by $\text{Adv}_{\text{HE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda) = \left| \mathbb{P} \left[\text{Exp}_{\text{HE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda) \rightarrow \text{true} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \right|$ is negligible in λ , where the experiment is defined as follows:*

$\text{Exp}_{\text{HE}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda)$:
 $\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}; L \leftarrow \emptyset$
 $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{KGen}(1^\lambda)$
 $\beta' \leftarrow \mathcal{ADV}(1^\lambda, \text{pk}, \text{evk}, : \mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-HE}})$
return $(\beta = \beta')$

<i>Oracles</i> $\mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-HE}}$	
<u>ENCRYPT</u> (pk, m_0, m_1) : If $m_0, m_1 \notin \mathcal{M}$: return \perp $c_\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Enc}(\text{pk}, m_\beta)$ $L \leftarrow L \cup \{c_\beta\}$ return c_β	<u>EVAL</u> ($\text{evk}, f, (c_1, \dots, c_n)$) : If $f \notin \mathcal{F}$: return \perp For $i \in [1, n]$ If $c_i \notin L$: return \perp $c \leftarrow \text{Eval}(\text{evk}, f, (c_1, \dots, c_n))$ $L \leftarrow L \cup \{c\}$ return c

Figure 2 – Oracles in the IND-HE-CPA game for an HE scheme HE and PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} : the encryption oracle ENCRYPT and the evaluation oracle EVAL.

The game keeps record of the queries made by \mathcal{ADV} through a list L storing all the ciphertexts it received. This includes encryption of a plain message sent by \mathcal{ADV} as well as ciphertexts resulting of the evaluation of a function f .

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5.4 Multi-Party Computation

MPC aims to create methods that enable different parties to jointly compute a function on their private data, while preserving privacy [11]. MPC was introduced as a secure two-party computation (2PC) by Andrew Yao [21] and was generalized into MPC by Goldreich, Micali, and Wigderson [22]. In 2PC settings [11], two parties jointly compute a function on their inputs without disclosing the values of their inputs to the other party. The most common techniques used in MPC are:

- Secret Sharing – Splitting a secret into multiple shares and distributing each share to a different party. The secret can only be recovered when all parties join shares [23]. The most commonly used form secret sharing is t -out-of- n Threshold Secret Sharing, where the secret message m is split into n random shares (where n is the number of parties), so that the sum of at least t shares is equal to m [24]. More specifically, it can be defined as follows:

Definition 6 (Threshold Secret Sharing). *Let $m \in \mathcal{M}$ be a message, $t, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $t \leq n$ then a TSS scheme is a tuple of the following algorithms $\text{TSS} = (\text{Share}, \text{Reconstruct})$ such that:*

- $\text{Share}(m, t, n)$ – a probabilistic algorithm, that takes as input the message m , the threshold t and the amount of shares n and outputs n randomized shares of the message $s = (s_1, \dots, s_n)$.
- $\text{Reconstruct}((s_1, \dots, s_t))$ – a deterministic algorithm, that takes as input t or more shares and outputs the reconstructed message m .

TSS must hold the following properties:

- **Correctness** – Anyone who holds at least t shares can recover the message m . More specifically, for all $m \in \mathcal{M}$, for all $(s_1, \dots, s_n) \leftarrow \text{TSS.Share}(m, t, n)$ and for all t sized subsets, the following equation holds (for shares generated in group \mathbb{G} and group operation $+$ and its inverse):

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{t \leq n} s_i = m \mid (s_1, \dots, s_n) \leftarrow \text{TSS.Share}(m, t, n) \right] = 1$$

- **Security** – A malicious adversary \mathcal{ADV} , who sees fewer than some threshold number of shares t learns no information about the message m . More specifically, for all

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$m, m' \in \mathcal{M}$, for all subsets $T \subset \{1, \dots, n\}$ of size $t - 1$, the following holds:

$$\{\text{Share}(m, t, n)[T]\} \approx_c \{\text{Share}(m', t, n)[T]\}$$

where $\text{Share}(m, t, n)[T] := \{s_i : ((s_1, \dots, s_n) \leftarrow \text{Share}(m, t, n)) \mid i \in T\}$.

Threshold Secret Sharing can also be generalized to Additive Secret Sharing, when $t = n$.

- Oblivious Transfer (OT) – a protocol where a sender sends one of several possible pieces of information to a receiver without knowing which piece of information the receiver obtained.
- Garbled Circuits (GC) – a cryptographic protocol that enables two parties to jointly evaluate a function over their private inputs without the presence of a trusted party. In [11], Yao transforms any function into a securely-evaluated function by modeling it as a Boolean circuit. The inputs and outputs of each gate are masked so that the party executing the function cannot discern any information about the inputs or intermediate values of the function.

Function Secret Sharing FSS is a novel MPC technique, which provides a way for additively secret-sharing a function f from a given function family F . More concretely, a two-party FSS scheme splits a function $f : (0, 1)^n \rightarrow G$, for some abelian group G , into functions described by keys such that $f = f_0 + f_1$ and every strict subset of the keys hides f . Formally, a FSS scheme can be defined as [25]:

Definition 7 (Function Secret Sharing). *Let FSS be a 2-party Function Secret Sharing scheme, that for some functionality $f \in \mathcal{F}$ has a pair of PPT algorithms $\text{FSS} = (\text{KeyGen}, \text{EvalAll})$ such that:*

- $\text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f)$ – a probabilistic algorithm that takes as input the security parameter λ and some function f and outputs two different function shares (f_0, f_1) (also known as function keys),
- $\text{EvalAll}(j, f_j, m_{pub})$ – a deterministic algorithm that takes as input a bit $j \in \{0, 1\}$, the function key f_j , and the public data m_{pub} and outputs a share of the computed function on the public input data $f_j(m_{pub})$.

An FSS scheme must satisfy the following two properties:

- **Secrecy** – A single key $(f_0 \vee f_1)$ does not reveal any information about the original function f . More specifically, for all PPT \mathcal{ADV} , $\forall \lambda$ and $\forall f \in \mathcal{F}$ the advantage for \mathcal{ADV} to distinguish

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the function from a share is negligible from the following security game:

$\text{GameExp}_{\text{FSS},f}^{\text{ind-fss-b}}$	
<p><u>Game_{f_{ss}-real}:</u></p> <p><i>ADV sends:</i> <i>f and f' to CHAL</i></p> <p><i>CHAL computes:</i> <i>b ← Rand(·), where b ∈ {0, 1};</i> <i>If b = 0, (f₀, f₁) ← FSS.KeyGen(1^λ, f);</i> <i>Else, (f'₀, f'₁) ← FSS.KeyGen(1^λ, f');</i> <i>CHAL sends one part of f_b or f'_b to ADV</i></p> <p><i>ADV guesses:</i> <i>If received share f_b or f'_b belongs to f or f'</i></p>	<p><u>Game_{f_{ss}-imag}:</u></p> <p><i>ADV sends:</i> <i>f and f' to CHAL</i></p> <p><i>CHAL computes:</i> <i>b ← Rand(·), where b ∈ {0, 1};</i> <i>If b = 0, (f₀, f₁) ← Rand(·);</i> <i>Else, (f'₀, f'₁) ← Rand(·);</i> <i>CHAL sends one part of f_b or f'_b to ADV</i></p> <p><i>ADV guesses:</i> <i>If received share of f_b or f'_b belongs to f or f'</i></p>

- **Correctness** – adding the corresponding shares of the function, outputs the same result as the original function. More specifically, $\forall \lambda, \forall f \in \mathcal{F}$ and $\forall m \in \mathcal{M}$:

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\begin{array}{l} f_0(m_{pub}) + f_1(m_{pub}) = f(m) \\ (f_0, f_1) \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(1^\lambda, f) \\ m + \alpha \rightarrow m_{pub} \\ \alpha \leftarrow \text{Rand}(\cdot) \end{array} \right] = 1$$

5.5 Differential Privacy

Problem: Consider a scenario in which a data analyst **DA** wants to receive information, say $f(\mathbf{m})$, for a plaintext $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, \dots, m_n)$ whose encryption c is provided by a user **U**. If every entity follows the protocol, **DA** obtains a decryption key dk_f and retrieves $f(\mathbf{m})$. However, if **U** updates an entry of the plaintext to obtain $\mathbf{m}' = (m'_1, m_2, \dots, m_n)$, **DA** retrieves $f(\mathbf{m}')$ and gains specific information on m_1 and m'_1 . For instance, if the FE scheme is an IPFE scheme, **U** learns $m'_1 - m_1$ which results in a significant leakage. Ideally, to avoid this situation, an attacker should not be able to tell if a specific value m_i or m'_i was taken as input in the resulting computation $f(\mathbf{m})$. This is the principle behind Differential Privacy (DP). We define it more formally as follows.

Definition 8 (Differential Privacy (DP)). *We say that a cryptographic algorithm \mathcal{A} is ϵ -differentially private if for all subset $S \subseteq \text{Im}(\mathcal{ADV})$ and for all vectors $\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{m}' \in \mathcal{M}^n$ that differs by at most one entry,*

$$\mathbb{P}[\mathcal{ADV}(\mathbf{m}) \in S] \leq e^\epsilon \mathbb{P}[\mathcal{ADV}(\mathbf{m}') \in S]$$

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This definition can be extended to a weaker version, *approximate* DP, more suitable for realistic and practical scenarios. This is the notion we consider for most cryptographic applications.

Definition 9 (Approximate Differential Privacy). *We say that a cryptographic algorithm \mathcal{A} is (ϵ, δ) -differentially private if for all subset $\mathcal{S} \subseteq \text{Im}(\mathcal{ADV})$ and for all vectors $\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{m}' \in \mathcal{M}^n$ that differs by at most one entry,*

$$\mathbb{P}[\mathcal{ADV}(\mathbf{m}) \in \mathcal{S}] \leq e^\epsilon \mathbb{P}[\mathcal{ADV}(\mathbf{m}') \in \mathcal{S}] + \delta$$

The recent works of Zalonis *et al.* [26] shows that from any regular FE scheme can be constructed a (approximate) differentially private FE, using the notion of *noisy* FE, which introduces a noise during the decryption. However, this result is not completely true in practice. If such construction indeed guarantees DP, it does not ensure that the recovered result will be accurate as the noise introduced is not properly bounded. Therefore, we extend their idea and propose a construction that manages this noise in a straightforward way, using or transcribing HE/FE construction.

Claim: Given an FE scheme FE and an approximate HE scheme HE, one can construct a THF scheme THF that guarantees approximate DP and accurate results for a chosen bound. This construction relies on our transcribing HE/FE method, detailed in section 7.

Construction (Informal) : Let HE := (KGen, Enc, Eval, Dec) be an approximate homomorphic encryption scheme for scaling factor Δ and FE := (Setup, Enc, KDer, Dec) be an exact functional encryption scheme for message space \mathcal{M} and functionality space \mathcal{F} , such that

- For any parameter $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ and pair of keys $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{FE.Setup}(1^\lambda)$, msk lies in the message space \mathcal{M}_{HE} of HE;
- FE.KDer : $(\text{msk}, f) \mapsto (\text{msk}, f)$ is in the class of functions \mathcal{F}_{HE} ;
- There exists a representation of f such that f is in the plaintext space \mathcal{M}_{HE} .

Then, we can construct a DP-FE scheme $\text{FE}^* := (\text{Setup}^*, \text{Enc}^*, \text{KDer}^*, \text{Dec}^*)$ as follows:

- $\text{Setup}^*(1^\lambda)$. The setup algorithm takes on input a security parameter λ ; generates the homomorphic keys $(\text{sk}, \text{pk}, \text{evk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{HE.KGen}(1^\lambda)$ and the FE keys $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{FE.Setup}(1^\lambda)$, computes $c_{\text{msk}} \xleftarrow{\$} \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(\text{msk}, \Delta)$ and outputs the secret key sk , and the public parameters $(c_{\text{msk}}, \text{mpk}, \text{evk})$;
- $\text{Enc}^*(\text{mpk}, m)$. The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of public key mpk and a message m in the message space \mathcal{M} , outputs a ciphertext $c \xleftarrow{\$}$

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$\text{FE.Enc}_{\text{mpk}}(m)$;

- $\text{KDer}^*(c_{\text{msk}}, \text{evk}, f)$. The key derivation algorithm is a deterministic algorithm. On input it takes the homomorphically encrypted key c_{msk} , the evaluation key evk and a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$. It encrypts homomorphically the function f into $c_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.Enc}_{\text{pk}}(f)$ and outputs a homomorphically encrypted decryption key $\text{HE.Eval}_{\text{evk}}(\text{FE.KDer}, (c_{\text{msk}}, c_f, \Delta)) \rightarrow c_{\text{dk}_f}$;
- $\text{Dec}^*(\text{sk}, c_{\text{dk}_f}, c)$; The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm. On input it takes the secret homomorphic key sk , a homomorphically encrypted decryption key c_{dk_f} and a ciphertext c ; computes $\text{HE.Dec}_{\text{sk}}(c_{\text{dk}_f}) \rightarrow \text{dk}_f + \delta$ and outputs a result $\text{FE.Dec}(\text{dk}_f, c) \rightarrow \text{res}$, where δ is a small noise that depends on Δ .

Correctness: For all parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\text{sk}, c_{\text{msk}}, \text{mpk}, \text{evk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Setup}^*(1^\lambda)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $\text{KDer}^*(c_{\text{msk}}, \text{evk}, f) \rightarrow c_{\text{dk}_f}$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}$,

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\left| \text{Dec}^*(\text{sk}, c_{\text{dk}_f}, \text{Enc}^*(\text{mpk}, m)) - f(m) \right| > B(\Delta) \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

where $B(\Delta) \in \mathbb{Q}$ is a positive bound that depends on Δ .

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6 Multi-Input and Multi-Client Functional Encryption

6.1 Additional Definitions

6.1.1 Multi-Input Functional Encryption (MIFE)

Functional Encryption is a powerful tool to perform fine-grained operations on encrypted data. However, its standard definition as presented in *definition 3* is limited to a single user. That is, if an external analyst wants to run computations using the functional decryption key, she is limited to data provided by a single user, hence limiting the relevance of the information retrieved. A straightforward answer to this limitation is to generate a functional decryption that supports multiple ciphertexts.

Definition 10 (Multi-Input Functional Encryption (MIFE)). *A MIFE scheme for message space \mathcal{M} and class of functions \mathcal{F} , consists of four PT algorithms Setup, KDer, Enc, Dec defined as follows:*

- Setup (1^λ). *The setup algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a security parameter λ it outputs a master secret key msk and a master public key $\text{mpk} := (\text{pk}_1, \dots, \text{pk}_n)$;*
- Enc (pk_i, m_i). *The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a public key pk_i and a message m_i in the message space \mathcal{M} , it outputs a ciphertext c_i . One also writes $c_i \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}_i}(m_i)$;*
- KDer (msk, f). *The key derivation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of the secret key msk and a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$, it outputs a decryption key dk_f . One also writes $\text{dk}_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f)$;*
- Dec (dk_f, \mathbf{c}). *The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that, on the input of a decryption key dk_f and a vector of ciphertexts $\mathbf{c} := (c_1, \dots, c_n)$, it outputs a result res . One also writes $\text{Dec}(\text{dk}_f, \mathbf{c}) \rightarrow \text{res}$.*

Correctness: *For all set of parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $\text{dk}_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f)$ and $\mathbf{m} = (m_1, \dots, m_n) \in \mathcal{M}^n$,*

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\text{Dec}_{\text{dk}_f}(c_1, \dots, c_n) \neq f(m_1, \dots, m_n) \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

where $c_i \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{\text{pk}_i}(m_i)$, $\forall i \in [n]$.

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6.1.2 Multi-Client Functional Encryption (MCFE)

MIFE supports ciphertexts coming from many users, but for ciphertexts encrypted with a single master public key. Even though this key is constituted of n sub-keys, it is accessible to any party of the system. This is not a limitation by itself, but some system models require each user to use their own encryption key, giving them more control on the data they share and how an external analyst can use them. A solution to do so is to introduce what we call a *label* during the encryption process.

Definition 11 (Multi-Client Functional Encryption (MCFE)). *A MCFE scheme for message space \mathcal{M} , label space \mathcal{L} and class of functions $\mathcal{F} : \mathcal{M}^n \times \mathcal{L}^{n+1} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$, consists of four PT algorithms Setup, KDer, Enc, Dec defined as follows:*

- Setup (1^λ) . *The setup algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a security parameter λ it outputs a master secret key msk and a master public key mpk := (pk_1, \dots, pk_n) ;*
- Enc (pk_i, m_i, ℓ_i) . *The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of a public key pk_i , a message m_i in the message space \mathcal{M} and a label ℓ_i , it outputs a ciphertext $c_{\ell,i}$. One also writes $c_{\ell,i} \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{pk_i}(m_i, \ell_i)$;*
- KDer (msk, f, ℓ) . *The key derivation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of the secret key msk, a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$ and a label ℓ , it outputs a decryption key $dk_{f,\ell}$. One also writes $dk_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f, \ell)$;*
- Dec $(dk_{f,\ell}, \mathbf{c})$; *The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm that, on the input of a decryption key $dk_{f,\ell}$ and a vector of ciphertexts $\mathbf{c} := (c_{\ell,1}, \dots, c_{\ell,n})$, it outputs a result res or \perp . One also writes $\text{Dec}(dk_{f,\ell}, \mathbf{c}) \rightarrow \text{res}$.*

Correctness: *For all set of parameters $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$, $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $dk_{f,\ell} \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{KDer}_{\text{msk}}(f)$ and $(m_1, \dots, m_n) \in \mathcal{M}^n$,*

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\text{Dec}_{dk_{f,\ell}}(c_{\ell,1}, \dots, c_{\ell,n}) \neq f(m_1, \dots, m_n, \ell_1, \dots, \ell_n, \ell) \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda)$$

where $c_{\ell,i} \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{Enc}_{pk_i}(m_i, \ell_i)$, $\forall i \in [n]$.

In a lot of application cases, f can be defined as $f'(m_1, \dots, m_n) \wedge [\ell_1 == \dots == \ell_n == \ell]$, that outputs either \perp if at least one of the labels ℓ_i or ℓ is different from another, or the result of a function f' that operates over \mathcal{M}^n as in the general MIFE case.

If MCFE was originally designed to give more control to users on their data, we highlight that its range of application goes beyond that. For instance, the label ℓ can be used as a time

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stamp to prevent the decryption of ciphertexts encrypted at different times, or in every situation in which the users need to have more access control on their data. Additionally, it can be used to give more access control on the decryption key generated, hence allowing a better management of the analysts capabilities and narrowing the leakage produced during the key derivation. Having identified this asset, we designed FE[r]Chain, a verifiable IPFE scheme that supports multi-clients.

6.2 FE[r]Chain

6.2.1 System and Threat Model

System Model: The system model we consider consists of three entities: (i) Key Curator (\mathcal{C}), (ii) Users (\mathcal{U}), (iii) Analyst (\mathcal{A}).

- **Key Curator (\mathcal{C}):** We assume the existence of an authority \mathcal{C} , which is responsible for the Setup phase and the generation of the decryption keys upon request of an analyst for a specific vector.
- **Users (\mathcal{U}):** Let $\mathcal{U} = u_1, \dots, u_n$ be a set of users holding sensitive data. They each encrypt their data under the public parameters generated by the curator and send them to the latter. The n users involved in the system individually encrypt their sensitive data into ciphertext using the public parameters generated by \mathcal{C} . Then, they send their encrypted data to the curator.
- **Analyst (\mathcal{A}):** We consider an external data analyst \mathcal{A} who expects the result of selective computation on the data held by the users. \mathcal{A} interacts with the curator and sends functional queries to \mathcal{C} .

Threat Model: The curator \mathcal{C} generates the master key through the Setup phase and administers the data collection infrastructure. We consider a typical crowd-sensing scenario in which users submit their data and obtain rewards for them (see for example [27]). Hence, \mathcal{C} has access to all data. However, consumers of these data are *not* expected to trust the curator to provide them with the correct results. Therefore, we do not require \mathcal{C} to be trusted by an analyst \mathcal{A} and consider the possibility that \mathcal{C} sends the wrong decryption key to mislead the results of the analyst or that he does not send the data at all during the transaction. On the user side, we reasonably consider that the users are honest in the data they provide, but they are not compelled to trust each other.

In terms of security, we assume that the curator does not collude with the analyst, as this would provide the analyst with access to all user data. This assumption is reasonable in our use case since we address the problem of exchanging data for a *fee* between the curator and the analyst.

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Concerning this exchange, we expect the scheme to meet the following security requirements (i) *Atomicity/Fairness*: either both the analyst and the curator respectively get a correct decryption and payment, or the transaction is aborted and neither party gets anything. Essentially, it is crucial to ensure that the curator is not paid without the correct computation of the functional query, and the analyst cannot evade payment after obtaining the correct computation result from the curator. (ii) *Confidentiality*: computation results should be protected against eavesdroppers or malicious entities looking to acquire information about plaintexts associated with ciphertexts.

We highlight again that users trust the curator with their data as they have already been rewarded for them. Furthermore, this is required in a classical IPFE setup: given the capability to generate a decryption key for arbitrary vectors, \mathcal{C} can compute trivial inner products on the ciphertexts hence recovering the plain data. The construction of IPFE schemes that do not rely on a trusted authority requires a decentralized setup [28, 29]. In this type of construction, the users themselves generate the decryption keys which implies a constant online involvement and is not suitable for the fair-exchange application we propose.

6.2.2 Constructing a Verifiable MCIPFE

Consider a scenario where a data analyst wants to perform selective computations on sensitive data $\mathbf{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_n)$ held by a single user. In this scenario, a key curator runs the Setup algorithm, sets mpk as public information, and keeps msk secret. The user encrypts the message \mathbf{x} into a ciphertext $\mathbf{c} = (c_1, \dots, c_n) \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(\text{mpk}, \mathbf{x})$. The analyst, who has access to \mathbf{c} , wants to calculate $\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle$ for a vector \mathbf{y} . Therefore, she sends a request to the curator to obtain the functional decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}$. The curator, given the analyst's vector \mathbf{y} and secret key msk , produces the decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}$ through KeyGen and sends it back to the analyst. Finally, the latter can use Decrypt to obtain the result.

In this scenario, we require the decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}$ to be specific to a ciphertext or set of ciphertexts. This restriction permits better access control and is recommended in the use case we consider, where an analyst purchases specific results. This can be achieved using an MCIPFE construction that we define in definition 11.

Label Encoding: To construct an MCIPFE, we design an encryption and decryption procedure that allows a user to encrypt a ciphertext under a specific label $\ell \in \mathbb{N}$. To ensure this specificity hence the security of the protocol, it is necessary to verify that, given a decryption key for a label ℓ , an adversary can not forge a decryption key for another label ℓ' . As the decryption key relies on an inner product, the multi-client decryption key can not be linear in ℓ . Therefore, we consider an encoding method $\text{Ecd} : \mathbb{Z} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}^n; \ell \mapsto (\ell_1, \dots, \ell_n)$ where each

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ℓ_i depends non-linearly on ℓ . This idea has already been proposed by Abdalla *et al.* [30] for the general case using on a *pseudo-random function* $\text{PRF}(i, \ell)$ as a basis for their encoding. However, this general approach is not the best choice for our protocol which relies on a public encoding. Therefore, we believe that the use of a hash function would be sufficient to guarantee the non-linearity of the encoding and the unforgeability of a label ℓ , as detailed in theorem 2, while providing better performances and better flexibility on the choice of labels.

Specification: we use a simple first and second pre-image resistant cryptographic hash function $H : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{n \cdot p}$. The output of the hash h can be split afterwards into n components of range p with a canonical projection $\pi : h := h_{n-1} \parallel \dots \parallel h_0 \mapsto (h_{n-1}, \dots, h_0)$. Eventually, given as input a label ℓ , we define the following encoding algorithm:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ecd} : \{0, 1\}^* &\rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_{n \cdot p} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_p^n \\ \ell &\mapsto H(\ell) \mapsto (\ell_1, \dots, \ell_n) \end{aligned}$$

Protocol 1 (MCIPFE scheme under the DDH- f assumption). Our MCIPFE scheme $\text{FE}[r]\text{Chain}$ consists of 4 algorithms (Setup, Encrypt, KeyGen, Decrypt) described in fig. 3.

Where (Gen, Solve) is a pair of algorithms defined as defined as:

- Gen $(1^\lambda, 1^\mu)$: As input two security parameters $\lambda \leq \mu$. Outputs $\text{pp} = (p, \tilde{s}, g, f, G, F)$ with: p a random μ -bit prime, $G = \langle g \rangle$ a finite group of order $n = ps$ s.t. $\text{gcd}(p, s) = 1$, \tilde{s} an upper bound for s s.t. the distribution $\{g^r, r \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, \dots, \tilde{s} \cdot p\}\}$ is indistinguishable from the uniform distribution on G . The DL problem is easy on $F = \langle f \rangle$, the subgroup of G of order p .
- Solve (p, pp, X) : A deterministic algorithm that solves the DL problem in F in a polynomial time.

Correctness: Let us verify that $\text{Decrypt}(\text{mpk}, \text{dk}_y^{(\ell')}, \mathbf{c}^{(\ell)})$ indeed outputs $\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle$ if and only if $\ell = \ell'$.

$$\begin{aligned} c_y &= \prod_{i=1}^n c_i^{y_i} / \left((g^r)^{s_y} (h^r)^{t_y} \right) \\ &= \prod_{i=1}^n \left(f^{x_i} (g^{s_i} \cdot h^{t_i})^{r \ell_i} \right)^{y_i} / \left(g^r \sum s_i y_i \ell_i h^r \sum t_i y_i \ell_i \right) \\ &= f^{\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle} g^r \sum s_i y_i \ell_i h^r \sum t_i y_i \ell_i / \left(g^r \sum s_i y_i \ell_i h^r \sum t_i y_i \ell_i \right) \\ &= f^{\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle} g^r \sum s_i y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) h^r \sum t_i y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 3 – MCIPFE algorithms

Then compute $\text{sol} \leftarrow \text{Solve} (p, pp, c_y)$ that is

$$\begin{aligned} \text{sol} &= \text{Solve} \left(p, pp, f^{\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle} g^r \sum s_i y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) h^r \sum t_i y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) \right) \\ &= \langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle \text{ iff } g^r \sum y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) (s_i + \alpha t_i) = 1 \end{aligned}$$

This last equality is obviously achieved if $\ell = \ell'$. In the case $\ell \neq \ell'$, some values of $(r, \mathbf{y}, s, \alpha, t)$ can inevitably output a valid result. However, we argue in section 6.3 that without the knowledge of r, α, s and t , a malicious analyst can neither forge such a tuple $(r, \mathbf{y}, s, \alpha, t)$ nor verify the validity of an output, rendering the decryption useless. Considering this observation, we

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assume that the algorithm outputs \perp if $\ell \neq \ell'$. This concludes the correctness.

The curator starts by running the Setup algorithm to generate the public parameters (p, \tilde{s}, f, g, h) , the secret keys s, t and the public keys h_1, \dots, h_n . As mentioned earlier, the user chooses a label ℓ and encrypts data with Encrypt, generating a ciphertext $\mathbf{c} = (c_0, c_1, \dots, c_n)$, where c_0 is a hint used for the decryption. Now, consider an analyst wishing to retrieve $\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle$ for a vector \mathbf{y} . She sends the curator a request \mathbf{y} for the ciphertext \mathbf{c} of \mathbf{x} , which provides the functional decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}} = (\sum s_i y_i \ell_i, \sum t_i y_i \ell_i)$ – output of KeyGen, for the label ℓ under which \mathbf{x} is encrypted. By running the Decrypt algorithm, the analyst can finally retrieve the desired quantity $\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle = y_1 x_1 + \dots + y_n x_n$.

Multi-Client Feature: The multi-client construction presented in definition 11 allows a user to encrypt messages through different labels and divide the set of encrypted data into smaller subsets. In protocol 1, this feature allows the curator to add a dependency between the decryption key and the ciphertext. Therefore, an analyst holding a decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}^{(\ell)} \leftarrow \text{KeyGen}(msk, \mathbf{y}, \ell)$ can only compute $\langle \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x} \rangle$ for \mathbf{x} encrypted under the same label ℓ . Consecutively, to restrict the access of a data analyst to a set of data, it is necessary to change the label of further encrypted data. In particular, if the curator wishes to sell a single computation, it is possible to deliver a functional decryption key specific to a single ciphertext encrypted with a specific label.

6.2.3 Verifiable decryption for MCIPFE

We propose a method that an analyst can use to verify the correctness of the decryption key $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}$ provided by the curator. In case the analyst receives an incorrect value for $\text{dk}_{\mathbf{y}}$ during a transaction, he can either cancel the transaction or request a refund from the curator.

Zero-knowledge proofs In this deliverable, we use non-interactive zero-knowledge (NIZK) to prove knowledge and relations over discrete logarithm values without the need for interaction. A zero-knowledge proof is an interactive protocol between a prover P and a verifier V , where the prover tries to convince the verifier about the validity of a statement without the verifier learning anything beyond this fact. Zero-knowledge proofs can be made non-interactive using the Fiat-Shamir heuristic.

We will be using the following standard notation introduced by Camenisch *et al.* [31] in describing such a proof. We will denote by:

$$\pi = \text{NIZK}\{(r, u, v) : C = g^r h^u \wedge I = g^v\}$$

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a non-interactive zero-knowledge proof, where the prover tries to convince the verifier that it knows r, u and v such that $C = g^r h^u$ and $I = g^v$. The variables r, u, v inside parentheses will denote private values, while C and I on the right will constitute public information available to the verifier V . Once π is created, V can test the validity of the proof submitted by the prover.

Functional Decryption Key Verification: A cryptographic protocol needs to meet several security assumptions to guarantee data privacy. Among these requirements, achieving ciphertext indistinguishability guarantees that a ciphertext does not reveal any information about the plaintext. However, in such cases, how can an external user confirm that a given ciphertext is a valid encryption? This question is particularly important in the field of operations on encrypted data, such as functional encryption or homomorphic encryption, where an external party requests the output of a specific function. This question has been widely studied [32] due to the growing trend of multi-party computation (MPC).

In fig. 4, we propose a verification method for protocol 1 based on the discrete logarithm (DLOG). This algorithm is followed by a ZKP on DLOG to guarantee no additional leakage is produced on the messages or the secret key. Given an encryption c of the user's data, assume that an analyst wishes to purchase the encryption $\prod_{i=1}^n c_i^{y_i \ell_i}$. Recall that this encryption satisfies the equality

$$\prod_{i=1}^n c_i^{y_i \ell_i} = f(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) g^r \sum s_i y_i \ell_i h^r \sum t_i y_i \ell_i = f(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{g}_y$$

To verify that the analyst retrieves the correct result, it is sufficient to verify that the decryption key dk_y is indeed the right decryption key for the requested vector \mathbf{y} . We thereunder design the fig. 4, which allows an analyst to check this correctness exclusively using the information known to her.

```
Verify (mpk, dky, c0 = (gr, hr), ℓ):  
Encode (ℓ1, ..., ℓn) ← Ecd (ℓ)  
Compute v ← ∏i=1n hiyiℓi  
Compute gy ← ∏(gr)sy(hr)ty  
return 1 [logg(v) = loggr(gy)]
```

Figure 4 – MCIPFE verification algorithm

To perform the verification, the analyst needs access to the hint c_0 of the ciphertext of interest, with both the public and the functional decryption key. These are all public, hence the

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verification does not impact the security of the protocol. Considering her vector \mathbf{y} , the analyst computes:

$$\prod_{i=1}^n h_i^{y_i \ell_i} = \prod_{i=1}^n (g^{s_i} h^{t_i})^{y_i \ell_i} = \prod_{i=1}^n (g^{s_i + \alpha t_i})^{y_i \ell_i} = g^{\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ell_i (s_i + \alpha t_i)}$$

On the other hand, mark that:

$$\mathbf{g}_y = g^{r s_y} h^{r t_y} = g^{r \sum_{i=1}^n s_i y_i \ell_i} h^{r \sum_{i=1}^n t_i y_i \ell_i} = g^{r \sum_{i=1}^n y_i \ell_i (s_i + \alpha t_i)}$$

The analyst accepts the functional decryption key if $\log_{g^r}(\mathbf{g}_y) = \log_g(v)$ for $v = \prod_{i=1}^n h_i^{y_i \ell_i}$.

ZKP on DLOG: Since the discrete logarithm is not easy in G , the analyst cannot compute $\log_{g^r}(\mathbf{g}_y)$ or $\log_g(v)$. However, by using a ZKP she can ensure that the two quantities are indeed equal without leaking information about their actual values.

6.3 Security Analysis

This section provides a security analysis for our MCIPFE [protocol 1](#) and extends it to the multi-users variant. Secondly, we prove the security of our use-case protocol regarding the threat model defined in [section 6.2.1](#).

6.3.1 Security of the MCIPFE construction

We admit that the original construction of Castagnos *et al.* [17] is IND-CPA secure as defined in [Definition 4](#), and prove the following theorem 1.

Theorem 1. Let MCIPFE be the construction presented in [protocol 1](#). Then MCIPFE is IND-CPA secure under the DDH- f assumption.

Proof. To prove [theorem 1](#) we rely on a combination of games, \mathcal{G}_0 denoting the IPFE game for [17] and \mathcal{G}_1 the IPFE game for [protocol 1](#). We assume two algorithms **A** and **B** are executed simultaneously but independently in which **A** is the adversary of a challenger **C** in game \mathcal{G}_0 and **B** is also the challenger of adversary **A** in game \mathcal{G}_1 . We prove that if **A** wins then **B** also wins, i.e. the advantage of **A** is bounded by the advantage of **B**. Since [17] is IND-CPA, the advantage of **B** in \mathcal{G}_0 is negligible, and so is the advantage of **A** in game \mathcal{G}_1 , which concludes.

Setup of game \mathcal{G}_0 : First, **C** generates $\text{mpk}, \text{msk} \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda, 1^\mu)$ and sends mpk to **B**. The latter picks two messages $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2 \in \mathbf{Z}^n$ and sends them to **C**. **C** flips a random coin $b \in \{0, 1\}$, encrypts $\mathbf{c}_b \leftarrow \text{Encrypt}(\text{mpk}, \mathbf{x}_b)$ and sends \mathbf{c}_b back to **B**.

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Setup of game \mathcal{G}_1 : \mathbf{B} samples at random a label $\ell \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}$ and encodes it into $(\ell_1, \dots, \ell_n) \leftarrow \text{Ecd}(\ell)$. She creates a new master public key $\text{mpk}^{\mathbf{B}} \leftarrow (h_1^{\ell_1^{-1}}, \dots, h_n^{\ell_n^{-1}})$, where ℓ_i^{-1} is the inverse of ℓ_i modulo $p - 1$, and sends it to \mathbf{A} . Remark that $\text{mpk}^{\mathbf{B}}$ is a valid public key, as $h_i^{\ell_i^{-1}} = g^{s_i \ell_i^{-1}} h^{t_i \ell_i^{-1}}$ and $s_i \ell_i^{-1}$ follows a Gaussian distribution $\mathcal{D}_{\mathbb{Z}, \sigma'}$ where $\sigma' \geq \sigma$. The same stands for t_i . Eventually, she sends $\text{mpk}^{\mathbf{B}}$ to \mathbf{A} .

Queries: The challenge ciphertext c_b is a valid encryption for game \mathcal{G}_1 under label ℓ . Therefore, \mathbf{A} can send functional key queries for vectors y_1, \dots, y_n such that $\langle y_i, x_0 \rangle = \langle y_i, x_1 \rangle$. Each corresponding decryption key $\text{sk}_{y_i} = (y_i, s_{y_i}, t_{y_i})$ in game \mathcal{G}_0 is a valid decryption key in game \mathcal{G}_1 for the label ℓ .

Guess: The game \mathcal{G}_1 corresponding to the security game for [protocol 1](#), \mathbf{A} guesses the value of b with an advantage ϵ_A . Subsequently, \mathbf{B} guesses the value of b in game \mathcal{G}_0 with the same advantage $\epsilon_B = \epsilon_A$. Since we assumed [\[17\]](#) to be IND-CPA secure, our construction [protocol 1](#) is IND-CPA secure. \square

We now address the problem of the unforgeability of the decryption key mentioned in the proof of correctness of [protocol 1](#).

Theorem 2. Given a decryption key $\text{dk}_y^{(\ell')}$ for a vector y and label ℓ' , we show that an analyst \mathcal{A} can not recover a usable result from a ciphertext $c^{(\ell)}$ for $\ell \neq \ell'$

Proof. As stated, the decryption algorithm leads to $\langle x, y \rangle$ iff $g^r \sum y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) (s_i + \alpha t_i) = 1$. Recall that \mathcal{A} knows g^r and ℓ , that are public information from $c^{(\ell)}$, the public key $g^{s_i + \alpha t_i}$ for $i \in [n]$ and (y_i, ℓ'_i) that are information she owns. For each $i \in [n]$, $(g^r, g^{s_i + \alpha t_i}, g^{r(s_i + \alpha t_i)})$ is a DDH triplet. According to the DDH hardness assumption, the analyst can not distinguish $g^{r(s_i + \alpha t_i)}$ from g^d for $d \xleftarrow{\$} \mathbb{Z}_q$ with non-negligible probability. Consequently, \mathcal{A} can not adaptively choose y and ℓ so that $g^r \sum y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) (s_i + \alpha t_i) = 1$, unless $y_i (\ell_i - \ell'_i) = 0 \pmod p$ for every tuple y_i, ℓ_i, ℓ'_i . However, the hash function used for the encoding being pre-image resistant, it is not possible for \mathcal{A} to choose the label ℓ accordingly. This concludes the proof of unforgeability. \square

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7 FE/HE Tranciphering

High-Level Overview. To initiate our construction, the parties (i.e. user, curator, analyst) agree on an HE and an FE scheme. The user generates locally the master keys msk, mpk while the analyst has his own unique keys sk and pk . The encryption of the data is done as in a classic FE setup: The user encrypts his data using the master public key mpk . The main difference lies in the way functional decryption keys are generated. Instead of running the key derivation algorithm using msk and a function f , the curator only receives their encryption under the HE scheme, that is c_{msk} and c_f . More precisely, the user who owns msk , encrypts it homomorphically with pk and sends the result c_{msk} to the curator. At a later point, when an analyst wishes to calculate a function f on a set of data (ciphertexts), encrypts the function f homomorphically with pk and sends the result c_f to the curator. Following, the curator runs the homomorphic *evaluation* algorithm on the key derivation circuit. This technique is known as *tranciphering*. The output of this computation is a homomorphic encryption of the decryption key dk_f , that can only be decrypted by the party holding the corresponding secret key sk , for example a data analyst. The final result is obtained by running the classic FE decryption algorithm using the decryption key dk_f on encrypted data given by the user.

7.1 Homomorphic evaluation of FE circuits

Theorem 3 (Homomorphic Key Derivation). Let HE be an HE scheme and FE be an FE scheme. Let $FE.KDer : (msk, f) \mapsto FE.KDer(msk, f)$ be the 2-ary key derivation function. We make the following assumptions:

- For any parameter $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ and pair of keys $(msk, mpk) \xleftarrow{\$} FE.Setup(1^\lambda)$, msk lies in the message space \mathcal{M}_{HE} of HE;
- $FE.KDer$ is in the class of functions \mathcal{F}_{HE} ;
- There exists a representation of f such that f is in the plaintext space \mathcal{M}_{HE} .

Under these assumptions, the key derivation algorithm can be run homomorphically, that is for all parameters $(\lambda_1, \lambda_2) \in \mathbb{N}^2$, $(sk, pk, evk) \xleftarrow{\$} HE.KGen(1^{\lambda_1})$, $(msk, mpk) \xleftarrow{\$} FE.Setup(1^{\lambda_2})$, $c_{msk} := HE.Enc_{pk}(msk)$, and $f \in \mathcal{F}_{FE}$:

$$HE.Eval_{evk}(FE.KDer, c_{msk}, HE.Enc_{pk}(f)) \in \text{Im}(HE.Enc_{pk}(dk_f)) \quad (1)$$

with overwhelming probability in λ_1, λ_2 .

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7.2 FE/HE transciphering definition

Definition 12 (Transciphering Homomorphic Functional (THF) Encryption Scheme). *Let $HE := (KGen, Enc, Eval, Dec)$ be a homomorphic encryption scheme and $FE := (Setup, Enc, KDer, Dec)$ be an exact functional encryption scheme for message space \mathcal{M} and functionality space \mathcal{F} , such that*

- *For any parameter $\lambda \in \mathbb{N}$ and pair of keys $(msk, mpk) \xleftarrow{\$} FE.Setup(1^\lambda)$, msk lies in the message space \mathcal{M}_{HE} of HE ;*
- *$FE.KDer : (msk, f) \mapsto (msk, f)$ is in the class of functions \mathcal{F}_{HE} ;*
- *There exists a representation of f such that f is in the plaintext space \mathcal{M}_{HE} .*

A THF encryption scheme THF for message space \mathcal{M} and class of functions \mathcal{F} consists of five PT algorithms THF.Setup, THF.Encap, THF.Enc, THF.KDer, THF.Dec defined as follows:

- *THF.Setup (1^λ) . The setup algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On input it takes a security parameter λ ; computes $(sk, pk, evk) \xleftarrow{\$} HE.KGen(1^\lambda)$ and outputs the secret key sk , the public key pk and the evaluation key evk ;*
- *THF.Encap $(1^\mu, pk)$. The encapsulation algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm that takes on input a security parameter μ and the public key pk . It generates the master secret and public keys $(msk, mpk) \xleftarrow{\$} FE.Setup(1^\mu)$, encrypts $c_{msk} \xleftarrow{\$} HE.Enc_{pk}(msk)$ and outputs the master public key mpk and the homomorphically encrypted master secret key c_{msk} ;*
- *THF.Enc (mpk, m) . The encryption algorithm is a probabilistic algorithm. On the input of public key mpk and a message m in the message space \mathcal{M} , outputs a ciphertext $c \xleftarrow{\$} FE.Enc_{mpk}(m)$;*
- *THF.KDer (c_{msk}, evk, f) . The key derivation algorithm is a deterministic algorithm. On input it takes the homomorphically encrypted key c_{msk} , the evaluation key evk and a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$. It encrypts homomorphically the function f into $c_f \xleftarrow{\$} HE.Enc_{pk}(f)$ and outputs a homomorphically encrypted decryption key $HE.Eval_{evk}(FE.KDer, (c_{msk}, c_f)) \rightarrow c_{dk_f}$;*
- *THF.Dec (sk, c_{dk_f}, c) ; The decryption algorithm is a deterministic algorithm. On input it takes the secret homomorphic key sk , a homomorphically encrypted decryption key c_{dk_f} and a ciphertext c ; computes $HE.Dec_{sk}(c_{dk_f}) \rightarrow dk_f$ and outputs a result $FE.Dec(dk_f, c) \rightarrow res$.*

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Correctness: For all parameters $\lambda, \mu \in \mathbb{N}$, $(sk, pk, evk) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{THF.Setup}(1^\lambda)$, $(mpk, c_{msk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{THF.Encap}(1^\mu, pk)$, $f \in \mathcal{F}$, $\text{THF.KDer}(c_{msk}, evk, f) \rightarrow c_{dk_f}$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}$,

$$\mathbb{P} \left[\text{THF.Dec}(sk, c_{dk_f}, \text{THF.Enc}(mpk, m)) \neq f(m) \right] = \text{negl}(\lambda, \mu)$$

7.3 Semantic Security of THF

This section provides a detailed and formal definition of the semantic security required for a THF scheme. In addition, we formally demonstrate the semantic security of THF with respect to our definition. This definition relies on the traditional notion of IND-CPA security for HE and FE, since it is the most commonly used paradigms. We provide theorem 4, that ensures the theoretical security of THF, given that HE and FE are IND-CPA secure.

Similarly to the security of FE defined in definition 4, we formalize IND-CPA through a security game. The challenger picks randomly $\beta \in \{0, 1\}$, generates the keys, encapsulates the master secret key, and sends the public parameters to \mathcal{ADV} ; that is the master public key mpk , the evaluation key evk and the encapsulation c_{msk} . The adversary subsequently requests functional decryption keys for functions of its choice. \mathcal{ADV} eventually sends two messages m_0, m_1 to the challenger, which replies with c_β . The scheme is IND-CPA secure if \mathcal{ADV} cannot guess the value of β with probability greater than $1/2 + \text{negl}$. More formally, the security game is described below:

Definition 13 (IND-CPA Security for THF (IND-THF-CPA)). *Let THF be a THF scheme for message space \mathcal{M} and functionality space \mathcal{F} . We say that THF is IND-THF-CPA if for all PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} , it holds that the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} :*

$$\text{Adv}_{\text{THF}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda, \mu) = \left| \mathbb{P} \left[\text{Exp}_{\text{THF}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda, \mu) \rightarrow \text{true} \right] - \frac{1}{2} \right|$$

is negligible in λ and μ , where the experiment is defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{Exp}_{\text{THF}, \mathcal{ADV}}^{\text{ind-cpa}}(\lambda, \mu):} \\ & \beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}; L_M \leftarrow \emptyset; L_F \leftarrow \emptyset \\ & (sk, pk, evk) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda) \\ & (mpk, c_{msk}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Encap}(1^\mu, pk) \\ & \beta' \xleftarrow{\$} \mathcal{ADV}(1^\lambda, 1^\mu, mpk, pk, evk : \mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-THF}}) \\ & \text{return } (\beta = \beta') \end{aligned}$$

As for FE, the game keeps record of the queries made by \mathcal{ADV} through a list L_M storing all the encryption queries and a list L_F storing each functional queries, represented as $(f_0, f_1, c_{dk_{f_\beta}})$, where f_0, f_1 are the queried functions and $c_{dk_{f_\beta}}$ is the output of the THF key

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Oracles $\mathcal{O}_{\text{ind-THF}}$

<p>ENCRYPT (mpk, m_0, m_1)</p> <p>If $m_0, m_1 \notin \mathcal{M}$: return \perp</p> <p>If $\exists (f_0, f_1, c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}}) \in L_F$; $f_0(m_0) \neq f_1(m_1)$: return \perp</p> <p>$c_\beta \xleftarrow{\\$} \text{Enc}(\text{mpk}, m_\beta)$</p> <p>$L_M \leftarrow L_M \cup \{(m_0, m_1, c_\beta)\}$</p> <p>return c_β</p> <p>EVAL ($\text{evk}, g, (c_{\text{dk}_{f_1}}, \dots, c_{\text{dk}_{f_n}})$) :</p> <p>If $g \notin \mathcal{F}_{\text{HE}}$: return \perp</p> <p>For $i \in [1, n]$:</p> <p> If $c_{\text{dk}_{f_i}} \notin L_F$: return \perp</p> <p> $f_0 \leftarrow g(\{f_{i0}\}_i), f_1 \leftarrow g(\{f_{i1}\}_i)$</p> <p> $c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}} \leftarrow \text{Eval}_{\text{evk}}(g, (c_{\text{dk}_{f_1}}, \dots, c_{\text{dk}_{f_n}}))$</p> <p> $L_F \leftarrow L_F \cup \{(f_0, f_1, c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}})\}$</p> <p>return c</p>	<p>KEYDER (f_0, f_1)</p> <p>If $f_0, f_1 \notin \mathcal{F}$: return \perp</p> <p>If $\exists (m_0, m_1) \in L_M$; $f_0(m_0) \neq f_1(m_1)$: return \perp</p> <p>$c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}} \xleftarrow{\\$} \text{KDer}(c_{\text{msk}}, f_\beta)$</p> <p>$L_F \leftarrow L_F \cup \{(f_0, f_1, c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}})\}$</p> <p>return $c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}}$</p> <p>DECRYPT ($c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}}$)</p> <p>If $c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}} \notin L_F$: return \perp</p> <p>$\text{Dec}(\text{sk}, c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}}) \rightarrow \text{dk}_{f_\beta}$</p> <p>return dk_{f_β}</p>
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Figure 5 – Oracles in the IND-THF-CPA game for a THF scheme THF and PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} : The encryption oracle ENCRYPT, the key derivation oracle KEYDER, the evaluation oracle EVAL and a decryption oracle DECRYPT.

derivation algorithm. Each request is made under the condition that $f_0(m_0) = f_1(m_1)$, for any $(f_0, f_1, c_{\text{dk}_{f_\beta}}) \in L_F$ and $(m_0, m_1, c_\beta) \in L_M$. This condition is mandatory, as violating it gives \mathcal{ADV} an overwhelming advantage to distinguish $f_0(m_0)$ from $f_1(m_1)$. Note that the EVAL algorithm works slightly differently than in a classical HE scheme. Even though the output of the evaluation for a function g is a valid homomorphic ciphertext, it is not necessarily the encryption of a valid functional decryption key for, e.g. dk_g . However, \mathcal{ADV} can use this oracle to try to get valuable information for $\text{dk}_{f_1}, \dots, \text{dk}_{f_n}$. Finally, a decryption oracle DECRYPT outputs the functional decryption key $f(\text{dk}_{f_\beta})$ as in a traditional FE scheme.

Theorem 4. Let THF be a THF scheme built from an HE scheme HE and an FE scheme FE. If HE and FE are IND-HE-CPA and IND-FE-CPA secure respectively, then THF is IND-THF-CPA secure.

Proof. We prove theorem 4 through a sequence of games, starting with the genuine THF game and ending with a game where the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} is negligible. We denote ϵ_i the advantage of \mathcal{ADV} for game i and $\epsilon(\lambda)$ (resp. $\epsilon(\mu)$) its advantage for the HE (resp. FE) game.

Game 0: This is the initial genuine THF game defined in definition 13. The challenger initializes the game by flipping at random a bit $\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \{0, 1\}$. Then, the key generation goes as follows: on

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the one hand, a PPT adversary \mathcal{ADV} samples the homomorphic keys $(pk, sk, evk) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Setup}(1^\lambda)$ and forwards pk to \mathcal{C} who runs the encapsulation $(m_{sk}, c_{m_{sk}}) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Encap}(1^\mu, pk)$. \mathcal{ADV} has access to the oracles ENCRYPT, EVAL, KEYDER and EVAL. Eventually, \mathcal{ADV} outputs a guess β' on the value of β with an advantage ϵ_0 .

Game 1: This game is similar to the previous one, except that the oracle DECRYPT is replaced by an oracle DECRYPT_{G1} defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{DECRYPT}_{G1}(c_{dk_{f_\beta}})} : \\ & \text{If } c_{dk_{f_\beta}} \notin L_F : \text{return } \perp \\ & dk \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Im}(\text{FE.KDer}_{m_{sk}}) \\ & \text{return } dk \end{aligned}$$

In short, when \mathcal{ADV} calls the DECRYPT oracle, \mathcal{C} runs the DECRYPT_{G1} oracle instead, which returns a random functional decryption key dk as plain, as in the classical FE game. We prove thereunder that a PPT adversary cannot distinguish this game from the previous one (with a non-negligible advantage).

Claim 1. $|\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_1| \leq \epsilon(\mu)$, where $\epsilon(\mu)$ is the advantage of an efficient adversary that breaks the FE game.

To prove this claim, we consider a PPT adversary \mathcal{B} that breaks the IND-FE-CPA game with an advantage $\epsilon(\mu)$. \mathcal{ADV} constructs an oracle KEYDER_{G1} defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{KEYDER}_{G1}(f_0, f_1)} \\ & c_{dk_{f_\beta}} \xleftarrow{\$} \text{KEYDER}(f_0, f_1) \\ & dk_{f_\beta} \xleftarrow{\$} \text{DECRYPT}(sk, c_{dk_{f_\beta}}) \\ & \text{return } dk_{f_\beta} \end{aligned}$$

Note that the oracle KEYDER_{G1} is well-defined, as it only calls oracle accessible to \mathcal{ADV} . One also notices that KEYDER_{G1} corresponds to the classical key derivation oracle KEYDER defined in [Figure 1](#). Therefore, \mathcal{ADV} provides to \mathcal{B} the master public key mpk and access to the oracles ENCRYPT and KEYDER. \mathcal{B} plays the IND-FE-CPA game using these data and outputs to \mathcal{ADV} a guess β'' on the value β with an advantage $\epsilon(\mu)$, which concludes.

Game 2: This game proceeds as the previous one, except that we replace the KEYDER oracle with a new oracle KEYDER_{G2} , defined as follows:

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$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{KEYDER}_{\mathbb{G}_2}(f_0, f_1)} \\ & \text{If } f_0, f_1 \notin \mathcal{F} : \mathbf{return} \perp \\ & c \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Im}(\text{HE.Enc}) \\ & L_F \leftarrow L_F \cup \{(f_0, f_1, c)\} \\ & \mathbf{return} c \end{aligned}$$

In this game, when \mathcal{ADV} calls the KEYDER oracle, \mathcal{C} runs the output of $\text{KEYDER}_{\mathbb{G}_2}$ instead, and hence substitutes a random element of the ciphertext space to the encryption of f_β . We prove that a PPT adversary cannot distinguish this game from the previous one (with a non-negligible advantage).

Claim 2. $|\epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2| \leq \epsilon(\lambda)$, where $\epsilon(\mu)$ is the advantage of an efficient adversary that breaks the HE game.

To prove this claim, we reduce Game 2 to the IND-FE-CPA game defined in definition 5. We introduce an oracle $\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_2}$ defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_2}(m_0, m_1)} \\ & c_\beta \xleftarrow{\$} \text{KEYDER}(m_0, m_1) \\ & \mathbf{return} c_\beta \end{aligned}$$

As before, we consider a second PPT adversary \mathcal{B} that has an advantage $\epsilon(\lambda)$ in the IND-HE-CPA game. The oracle $\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_2}$ is well-defined, as it only calls oracle accessible to \mathcal{ADV} , and corresponds to the classical homomorphic encryption oracle ENCRYPT defined in Figure 2. During the IND-THF-CPA game, \mathcal{ADV} can forward (pk, evk) to \mathcal{B} . With access to both oracles EVAL and $\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_2}$, \mathcal{B} outputs a guess β'' on the value β with an advantage $\epsilon(\lambda)$, which concludes.

Game 3: This game proceeds as the previous one, except that we replace the ENCRYPT oracle with a new oracle $\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_3}$, defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \underline{\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_3}(\text{mpk}, m_0, m_1)} \\ & \text{If } m_0, m_1 \notin \mathcal{M} : \mathbf{return} \perp \\ & c \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Im}(\text{Enc}) \\ & \mathbf{return} c \end{aligned}$$

In this game, when \mathcal{ADV} calls the ENCRYPT oracle, \mathcal{C} runs the output of $\text{ENCRYPT}_{\mathbb{G}_3}$ instead, and hence substitutes a random element of the ciphertext space to the encryption of m_β . We prove that a PPT adversary cannot distinguish this game from the previous one (with a non-negligible advantage).

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Claim 3. $|\epsilon_3 - \epsilon_2| \leq \epsilon'(\mu)$, where $\epsilon'(\mu)$ is the advantage of an efficient adversary that breaks the FE game in the sense of PKE.

The key argument to prove this claim is that the functional encryption c_β is not used in any oracle but the encryption, as KEYDER has been replaced by random oracles in the previous games. Hence, distinguishing the output c_β of the algorithm ENCRYPT from a random element $c \xleftarrow{\$} \text{Im}(\text{FE.Enc})$ is reduced to a traditional IND-CPA game in the sense of PKE. The advantage $\epsilon'(\mu)$ of an efficient adversary \mathcal{ADV} in such game is negligible.

Conclusion: Every oracle of Game 3 is independent from β , hence \mathcal{ADV} has a nil advantage in Game 3. The overall advantage ϵ_{THF} of \mathcal{ADV} in the THF game defined in definition 13 is $\epsilon_{\text{THF}} \leq \epsilon(\mu) + \epsilon(\lambda) + \epsilon(\mu')$. As a finite sum of negligible elements, ϵ_{THF} is negligible, which concludes. \square

7.4 FE/HE protocol: CaTT

Overview of the protocol: **DA** generates the homomorphic keys (sk, pk, evk) on one side, and the user generates the functional keys (msk, mpk) on the other side. The latter encrypts msk into a ciphertext c_{msk} with the analyst's homomorphic key pk and encrypts m into a ciphertext c under his functional public key mpk . The analyst, who has access to c , wants to calculate $f(m)$. She first encrypts f under pk into c_f and sends a request to **KC** to obtain (an encryption of) the functional decryption key c_{dk_f} . The curator, given the encrypted function c_f , the encrypted master secret key c_{msk} and the evaluation key evk , runs homomorphically the functional key generation algorithm to output the encrypted decryption key c_{dk_f} . It then sends it back to the analyst who uses the homomorphic secret key sk to retrieve dk_f and finally $f(m)$.

System model: The model we consider consists of three entities: (i) Key Curator (**KC**), (ii) User (**U**) and (iii) Data Analyst (**DA**).

- **Key Curator (KC):** The curator is an authority responsible for the generation of decryption keys. Upon request of an analyst **DA** for a function f , **KC** is responsible for the generation of the corresponding decryption key dk_f ;
- **User (U):** The user is the owner of the data. He sets the system up by generating the functional parameters $(msk, mpk) \xleftarrow{\$} \text{FE.Setup}(1^\lambda)$ and sending $c_{msk} \xleftarrow{\$} \text{HE.Enc}_{pk}(msk)$ to **KC**, where pk is the public key of the analyst **DA** for the HE scheme.
- **Data Analyst (DA):** The analyst is an external party that wishes to learn the evaluation of a certain function f over data m provided by the user. With exclusive access to this as a ciphertext, **DA** sends a request for f to **KC**, which provides the corresponding decryption key dk_f , through which the result of the computation $f(m)$ can be obtained.

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Threat model: Concerning the *semantic* security (IND-CPA) and function-hiding, we rely on the analyses we provide in other sections, namely theorem 4 and section 7.5 respectively. Concerning the security of the protocol, We trust the user **U** with the information he sends, and assume that he provides genuine data, performs the encapsulation using the right homomorphic key pk and encrypts the data using the public key mpk . We do *not* require the key curator to be fully trusted. However, we make the assumption that **KC** and **DA** do *not* collude, as the knowledge of both c_{msk} and sk is sufficient to retrieve msk and hence decrypting every ciphertext produced by **U**

This last assumption is mandatory in most FE construction relying on a curator, trusted or not. Indeed, the curator has the capability to generate decryption key and the analyst to get valuable information from it. When implemented in practice, one assumes that **KC** will generate a reasonable amount of decryption keys – usually one. However, if it provides a larger number of decryption key, **DA** can bypass the limited information she is originally supposed to get.

Figure 6 – Description of CaTT

7.5 Function Hiding

Definition 14 (Informal). An FE scheme is said to be function-hiding if no PPT adversary, given two ciphertexts $c_1 \in \text{Im}(\text{Enc}(pk, m_1))$ and $c_2 \in \text{Im}(\text{Enc}(pk, m_2))$ and two decryption keys dk_{f_1} and dk_{f_2} for $f_1, f_2 \in \mathcal{F}$ such that $f_1(x_1) = f_2(x_2)$, can distinguish between f_1 and f_2 with non-negligible advantage.

We propose a systematic method to achieve function hiding in a public setup. This technique relies on the homomorphic encryption of f , prior to derivation. We present algorithm 1, which involves two parties: **DA** (data analyst) and **KC** (curator). In this scenario, **DA** sends a request

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Figure 7 – Description of CaTT for three parties U, KC and DA. FE algorithms are represented in dotted lines and HE algorithms in solid lines. Circles are used to highlight components in plain.

to **KC** to obtain a decryption key for a function f , while ensuring that f remains hidden from **DA**.

Algorithm 1: Function-Hiding Key Derivation

Input: HE keys (sk, pk, evk) , the master secret key msk and a function $f \in \mathcal{F}$

Output: the decryption key dk_f

- 1: **DA** encrypts $c_f \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.Enc}_{pk}(f)$ and sends it to **KC**
 - 2: **KC** encrypts $c_{msk} \stackrel{\$}{\leftarrow} \text{HE.Enc}_{pk}(msk)$
 - 3: **KC** runs $c \leftarrow \text{HE.Eval}_{evk}(\text{FE.KDer}(c_{msk}, \cdot), c_f)$ and sends it to **DA**
 - 4: **DA** decrypts $dk_f \leftarrow \text{HE.Dec}_{sk}(c)$
-

Function-Hiding: Assuming that **KC** knows the functional keys (msk, mpk) and the public homomorphic keys (pk, evk) , algorithm 1 is function-hiding.

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7.6 Experiments

To evaluate the practicality of our transciphering protocol, CaTT, we implemented a proof-of-concept, including the IPFE scheme of Mera *et al.* [33] and the Brakerski-Gentry-Vaikuntanathan (BGV) [34] scheme, using the *Python* programming language. For testing and benchmarking, we followed best practices by using the *pytest* and *pytest-benchmark* libraries. Additionally, we measured memory usage with the *memory-profiler* library. Our experiments were conducted in a single-threaded environment on a PC with an Intel Core i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz and 64GB of memory.

To ensure a solid comparison, we present benchmark results for IPFE and CaTT, including execution time, memory usage of different scheme functions, and storage costs associated with various data used during execution. Our comparison between a pure IPFE scheme and CaTT demonstrates that constructing a trustless functional encryption (FE) scheme without relying on trusted entities is not only feasible but also comes with a reasonable overhead.

7.6.1 Benchmarks

To benchmark IPFE and CaTT, we follow the notation and algorithms in section 7.4, using a modular approach for implementing schemes, where $FE = \{\text{Setup}, \text{KDer}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec}\}$ and $HE = \{\text{KGen}, \text{Enc}, \text{Eval}, \text{Dec}\}$. For simplicity, we denote the transciphering process as *Transcipher*. As shown in table 4, we define three parameter sets—Params = {S, M, L}—to evaluate performance across different system scales. The small set (**S**) uses input vectors m and functions f of length 50 with a polynomial ring degree of $\log_2 N = 5$. The medium set (**M**) extends this to a length of 500 with $\log_2 N = 6$, while the large set (**L**) increases it to 1000 with $\log_2 N = 7$. Additionally, table 4 provides the ciphertext modulus, plaintext modulus, and bounds on the input and function vectors, denoted as $\log_2 q, \log_2 p, B_x, B_y$.

Table 4 – Parameters for Test & Benchmark

Params	Vector Size	$\log_2 N$	$\log_2 q$	$\log_2 p$	B_x	B_y
Small	50	5	64	16	16	8
Medium	500	6	86	17	32	16
Large	1000	7	128	18	64	32

Running time and memory usage: As shown in table 5, the running time of IPFE functions increases with the change of parameters. For the smallest benchmark (**S**), where vectors have a length of 50, the Setup phase takes $22.2ms$, while Enc, KDer, and Dec take $24.3ms$, $4.6ms$, and $5ms$, respectively. For the most significant benchmark (**L**), with vectors of length 1000,

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Setup extends to $2,988ms$, and Enc, KDer, and Dec require $3,098ms$, $243.7ms$, and $231.6ms$, respectively. However, as shown in table 5, the memory usage of IPFE functions does not increase gradually. Even with larger vector lengths and input bounds, memory usage remains stable, averaging around $65MB$.

Similarly, as presented in table 6, the running time of CaTT functions increases as the parameters change. As expected, the execution times of the IPFE functions Setup, Enc, Dec within CaTT remain nearly identical to standalone IPFE, with minor variations due to benchmarking conditions that are negligible. Since CaTT employs BGV for transciphering, its running time is also reported. For the smallest benchmark (**S**), with vector length 50, HE.KGen takes $21.3ms$, while HE.Enc and HE.Dec take $47.8ms$ and $0.4ms$, respectively. In the largest benchmark (**L**), with vector length 1000, HE.KGen extends to $258ms$, and HE.Enc and HE.Dec require $6,192ms$ and $3.1ms$, respectively. Most importantly, in CaTT, the running time of Transcipher increases significantly, from $1054.7ms$ in benchmark (**S**) to $335,695.6ms$ in benchmark (**L**). However, as shown in table 6, the memory usage of CaTT functions does not increase gradually. Even with larger vector lengths and input bounds, memory usage remains stable, averaging around $84MB$.

Table 5 – Running Time and Memory costs of RLWE-based IPFE

Bench	Params	Time (ms)	Memory (MB)
Setup	S	22.2	55.99
	M	499.2	59.31
	L	2988	67.62
Enc	S	24.3	57.41
	M	521.1	61.56
	L	3098	76.99
KDer	S	4.6	67.51
	M	69.6	67.85
	L	243.7	70.69
Dec	S	5	67.06
	M	67.8	68.46
	L	231.6	76.50

Table 6 – Running Time and Memory costs of CaTT IPFE

Bench	Params	Time (ms)	Memory (MB)
FE.Setup	S	22.2	56.19
	M	494.5	59.20
	L	2967.5	67.73
HE.KGen	S	21.3	57.39
	M	62	57.44
	L	258	57.74
HE.Enc _{pk} (msk)	S	47.8	57.61
	M	1048.4	64.11
	L	6192	84.77
FE.Enc(mpk, m)	S	23.9	62.18
	M	520.9	63.78
	L	3096	77.26
HE.Enc _{pk} (f)	S	48.2	68.87
	M	1050.3	69.56
	L	6208.2	76.32
Transcipher	S	1054.7	68.68
	M	35720.6	72.43
	L	335695.6	112.72
HE.Dec _{sk} (c _{dk})	S	0.4	75.46
	M	1	79.22
	L	3.1	113.12
FE.Dec (dk _f , c _m)	S	5	77.98
	M	68.3	81.35
	L	247.8	112.96

* Transcipher : $HE.Eval_{evk}(FE.KDer, (c_{msk}, c_f))$

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Storage costs: As shown in table 7, the storage costs for various data in IPFE, including the message vector m , function f , master secret key msk , master public key mpk , FE-encrypted ciphertext c , functional decryption key dk_f , and the function result $f(m)$, are provided for three parameter sets. Note that the sizes of the message and function vectors are equal. As expected, increasing the vector length from 50 to 1000 and enlarging the plaintext and ciphertext modulus leads to higher storage costs. However, the rate of increase is more pronounced for master keys and ciphertexts due to the significant difference between ciphertext and plaintext modulus. For example, comparing benchmark (S) and (L), the size of msk grows from 7.73KB to 414.39KB, mpk increases from 24.83KB to 2,665.92KB, and c expands from 24.83KB to 2,665.94KB. Additionally, the ciphertext expansion rate ($\frac{c}{m}$) is approximately $225\times$ and $1353\times$ for benchmark (S) and (L), respectively. Overall, CaTT is $21.8\times$ slower than IPFE for benchmark (S), $32.8\times$ slower for benchmark (M), and $54.1\times$ slower for benchmark (L), while requiring $2.11\times$ more memory for benchmark (S), $2.12\times$ for benchmark (M), and $2.41\times$ for benchmark (L).

Similarly, as presented in table 8, the storage costs for CaTT include the same IPFE data as well as additional BGV components: secret key sk , public key pk , evaluation keys evk , homomorphically encrypted master secret key c_{msk} , homomorphically encrypted message c_m , plaintext function p_f , homomorphically encrypted function c_f , and homomorphically encrypted functional decryption key c_{dk_f} . These costs are provided for three parameter sets. As expected, the storage costs for m , f , msk , mpk , and $f(m)$ in CaTT are nearly identical to standalone IPFE, with minor variations due to benchmarking conditions that are negligible.

When examining the additional storage costs introduced by the BGV scheme, for benchmark (S), the total storage for sk and pk is less than 2KB, while evk requires 26.44KB. The storage costs for c_{msk} , c_m , c_f , and c_{dk_f} are 47.07KB, 24.26KB, 47.06KB, and 1.32KB, respectively. For benchmark (L), the total storage for sk and pk is less than 6.5KB, while evk requires 291.63KB. The storage costs for c_{msk} , c_m , c_f , and c_{dk_f} are 5,203.88KB, 2,602.64KB, 5,203.82KB, and 5.58KB, respectively. Similar to IPFE, the results show that the rate of size increase is higher for master keys and ciphertexts due to the significant difference between ciphertext and plaintext modulus. Overall, CaTT requires $3.11\times$ more storage than IPFE for benchmark (S), $2.80\times$ for benchmark (M), and $2.84\times$ for benchmark (L), with the ciphertext expansion rate ($\frac{c_m}{m}$) reaching $220\times$ for small vectors and $1321\times$ for large vectors.

Note on proof-of-concept: The comparison between the RLWE-based IPFE scheme and the CaTT highlights important trade-offs in security, performance, and resource consumption. While CaTT introduces additional overheads, these costs are justified by its ability to eliminate the need for a trusted entity, providing a fully trustless and secure solution.

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Despite these increases, the benefits of CaTT—removing the single point of trust and ensuring a secure scheme—make the additional computational, memory, and storage costs feasible and cost-effective. This trade-off is a reasonable price for achieving a trustless architecture, which is critical for modern cryptographic applications requiring robust security guarantees.

Table 7 – Storage Costs of RLWE-based IPFE

Name	S	Size (KB)	
		M	L
m	0.11	0.99	1.97
f	0.11	0.99	1.97
msk	7.73	118.68	414.39
mpk	24.83	529.48	2665.92
c	24.83	529.54	2665.94
dk_f	0.45	0.65	0.98
$f(m)$	0.01	0.01	0.02

Table 8 – Storage Costs of CaTT IPFE

Name	S	Size (KB)	
		M	L
m	0.11	0.99	1.97
f	0.11	0.99	1.97
msk	7.71	118.26	414.04
mpk	24.26	515.67	2602.61
sk	0.44	0.59	0.88
pk	1.32	2.46	5.59
evk	26.44	78.63	291.63
c_{msk}	47.07	1032.79	5203.88
c_m	24.26	515.66	2602.64
c_f	47.06	1032.77	5203.82
c_{dk_f}	1.32	2.45	5.58
dk_f	0.45	0.64	1.05
$f(m)$	0.01	0.01	0.02

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8 Analysing Related Literature

As mentioned, the HARPOCRATES project is linked to providing novel solution for operating on encrypted data. Due to this, we aimed to analyse the current state-of-the-art, primarily within the field of ML and even more specifically Privacy-Preserving Machine Learning (PPML).

ML allows interested parties (e.g. companies, researchers, etc.) to train models either locally or in an interactive distributed environment. Privacy is guaranteed in the scenario where a model is trained on a local machine, as in this case, no models or data are shared. However, there are concerns regarding the level of security when deploying ML in a distributed environment. For example, in a scenario where parties share their data to train a model. To address privacy concerns, various PPML techniques have been proposed. These PPML techniques take both ethical and legal concerns into account. Specifically, in privacy-preserving training, data privacy is demanded¹. In privacy-preserving MLaaS, model privacy is also necessary besides data privacy so that neither the client nor any other parties learn anything about the model parameters on cloud servers, other than what can be learned from the final prediction.

The main motivation behind this overview of related literature is to better understand the landscape of MLaaS in a data-sensitive context by employing PPML techniques. In this study, we focus primarily on the two cryptographic techniques: HE and MPC – that are employed in PPML training. As such, we cover 2 HE-based PPML solutions, one of which focuses on combining DP with HE for added robustness against privacy attacks, while the other provides a solution for that combines a distributed approach with HE to develop Multiparty HE (MHE) for secure model training. Additionally, we cover 17 MPC-based works, which allow computing model training through MPC techniques.

8.1 HE-based implementations:

Sphinx [35] – is a CKKS LHE scheme used for online training and inference on the cloud. The code is implemented with the Microsoft SEAL library for homomorphic operations and makes use of KANN² to implement ML models in C. Sphinx combines various improvements, such as batch packing, made in HE PPML training and inference to greatly reduce the communication overhead and computational complexity of ML operations. The authors improve HE multiplications by reducing the amount of rescaling and relinearization operations. They also use forward propagation caching and introduce a different encryption method, called zero encryption, to reduce communication costs. The implementation is tested on MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets

¹Neither the cloud server nor any other involved parties, learn anything about outsourced data of clients other than their size.

²<https://github.com/attractivechaos/kann>

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and shows reduced communication costs and computational complexity when compared to baseline HE. It reports higher throughput and lower latency than works such as SecureNN [36], SecureML [37] and CryptoDL [38]. Sphinx [35] makes use of DP to increase its resilience to data reconstruction attacks. The authors test their implementations resilience to a gradient matching attack, which aims to recover input images and their labels from the intermediate gradients [35]. From their testing, they show that Sphinx outperforms an equivalent DP-only defense mechanism irrespective to the chosen privacy parameters.

POSEIDON [39] – is a hybrid PPML implementation that makes use of federated learning and LHE techniques to produce Multiparty Homomorphic Encryption (MHE). POSEIDON's MHE implementation uses the CKKS scheme and an extended version of the Mouchet *et al.* [40] implementation. The implementation provides confidentiality for: (i) Training data, (ii) Model details and (iii) Evaluation data. Additionally, as the authors note POSEIDON achieves: (i) Flexibility – by eliminating the need for outsourcing data to other parties (ii) Security – by providing confidentiality for the data and model even in a honest minority setting (where $N - 1$ parties can be corrupted for an unbound N) (iii) Scalability – by reducing the communications overhead compared to other solutions. POSEIDON's accuracy and training time is similar to other SotA MPC techniques, such as SecureML [37], SecureNN [36] and Falcon [41].

8.2 MPC-based implementations

Over the past years, various methods focused on constructing MPC protocols with different properties and settings. However, as listing all the relevant techniques exceeds the scope of this work we recommend a well-written and friendly introduction to MPC [42]. Nevertheless, we intend to review the most important MPC approaches that perform PPML training among multiple parties and show their relationships in Figure 8. These works are discussed in detailed below. We categorize MPC techniques based on the number of parties involved in the protocol. This categorization can vary from a 2-party protocol, where training is conducted on two non-colluding parties, to a 4-party protocol, where the protocol can be carried out by four parties. The main motivation for increasing the number of parties in the MPC protocols can be twofold: (i) aiming for more efficient computations and collaborative tasks with the same amount of corruptions as in lower party variants, or (ii) improving security through increased resilience against more potential malicious parties. However, it is important to note that the specific security guarantees may vary depending on the chosen protocol and configuration.

Two-party Computation: The 2-party computation is a representative of MPC [43]. Many 2-party MPC based ML models have been developed among which SecureML [37], proposed by Mohassel *et al.*, was the first privacy-preserving protocol for efficient NN training. It is based on Secret Sharing protocol where the data owner distributes private data among two servers.

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Figure 8 – MPC Taxonomy – illustrates comparative framework employed in our study, showcasing performance evaluations among protocols. For example, Falco against SecureNN and ABY3, and SecureNN against SecureML.

Compared to previous SotA frameworks in PPML, SecureML is much faster than the protocol implemented in [44, 45], however, it is an order of magnitude slower than the privacy free counterparts. Though SecureML excels in certain aspects of PPML, its limitations in WAN settings (high number of interactions and communication overhead) prompt the exploration of alternative frameworks. QUOTIENT [46] emerges as a compelling choice, showcasing superior speed and accuracy in both WAN and LAN settings. Its core idea lies in ternarizing the network weights into integer values of $\{-1, 0, 1\}$ upon which the MPC-aware NN training protocols are developed. Compared to SecureML, training with QUOTIENT is $50\times$ faster in both WAN and LAN setting. By implementing ML features like adaptive gradients and the normalization approach, QUOTIENT reaches the level of accuracy of SecureML relatively fast – in less than two epochs. Furthermore, for the same network in SecureML, QUOTIENT achieves an overall accuracy of 99.38%, a 6% improvement over the SecureML (93.4%). In order to make a 2-party MPC technique even more efficient, a different approach is taken by ParSecureML [47]. ParSecureML, leveraging GPU-based parallelization, offers a substantial speedup, presenting a noteworthy alternative for efficient PPML.

It consists of three major parts: (i) Profiling-guided adaptive GPU utilization, (ii) double pipeline design for intra-node data transmission between CPU-GPU and (iii) compressed transmission for inter-node communication between two servers. These three components are integrated in order to enable 2PC on GPUs. Compared to SecureML [37], the authors show that ParSecureML achieves an average of $32.2\times$ speedup. Another notable work in the field of 2-party

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PPML is ABY2.0 [48]. ABY2.0 proposes a mixed-world MPC protocol between Arithmetic, Boolean and Yao sharing, based on which a NN training protocol was built. For NN training, ABY2.0 has $2.7\text{-}3.46\times$ and $2.4\text{-}2.8\times$ online throughput improvements for LAN and WAN settings respectively.

In a 2-party MPC protocol, where only two parties are involved, the threat model considered is a weaker semi-honest threat model (see Table 9). This model it assumes parties will follow the protocol and this might not always be the case in the real world. If one party is malicious, the system may not work effectively. To address this limitation and take full advantage of the benefits of MPC, aimed at facilitating secure collaboration among multiple distrustful parties, researchers are exploring ways to involve more than two parties. The primary goal of adding more parties is twofold: firstly, researchers aim to improve the training process by incorporating a larger dataset — more parties participating implies more data for training. Secondly, this expansion is intended to address a more realistic malicious threat model. This widens the applicability and enhances the security of MPC in real-world scenarios.

Table 9 – Comparison between privacy-preserving training methods using MPC

Framework	Year	Threat Model	Supported Layers					Techniques Used			LAN/WAN		Evaluation Dataset		Neural Network Architectures						
			Convolutional	ReLU	Maxpool	Linear	OT	GC	Secret Sharing	FSS	LAN	WAN	MNIST	CIFAR	Tiny ImageNet	ImageNet	From SecureML	From MiniCNN	LeNet	AlexNet	VGG16
2PC	SecureML	2017	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Quotient	2019	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	ParSecureML	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	ABY2	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	AriaNN	2022	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
3PC	ABY ³	2018	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	SecureNN	2019	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	BLAZE	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Falcon	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	SWIFT	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Adam in Private	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	CryptGPU	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Piranha	2022	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4PC	Trident	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Fantastic Four	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	MPCLeague	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Tetrad	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Three-party Computation: In 3-party MPC, only one protocol, CryptGPU [49], exclusively considers the weaker semi-honest threat model. Others take into account both threat models. For instance: *ABY³* [50] designs techniques for encrypted training of DNNs in the 3-party settings with a single corrupted server. This is a mixed protocol framework for ML, which uses MPC techniques and offers efficient support for fixed point arithmetic computation, improved matrix multiplication (to reduce the amount of communication) and an efficient piece-wise polynomial evaluation technique. *ABY³* experiments on both inference and training for LR, LoR and NN models. For training NNs, *ABY³* is $55,000\times$ faster than the 2PC solution of SecureML. Another significant contribution in the 3-party MPC settings is *SecureNN* [36], designed to ensure

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privacy against one malicious corruption and privacy and correctness against one semi-honest corruption. Prior works to SecureNN use boolean computation and Yao's Garbled Circuits (GC) to construct functions, such as ReLU, Maxpool and their derivatives. This results in increased communication cost. SecureNN's proposed protocols for Boolean computation require much lesser communication overhead than the cost of converting to a Yao encoding and executing a GC. Thanks to protocol efficiency, SecureNN is the first work to privately train a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) [51] with an accuracy of higher than 99% on MNIST. Compared to SecureML, SecureNN is $79\times$ faster in the LAN (latency 0.22 ms, bandwidth 625 MB/s) setting, and $553\times$ faster in the WAN setting (latency 58 ms, bandwidth 40 MB/s). In the 3-party LAN setting, SecureNN outperforms SecureML in training time by $7\times$. Moving forward, Patra and Suresh proposes a PPML framework named *BLAZE* [52] in the 3-party setting, tolerating one malicious corruption over a ring (\mathbb{Z}_{2^ℓ}). It consists of a data-independent preprocessing phase, used to perform a relatively expensive computation, and a fast input-dependent online phase. The authors benchmark the performance of the framework over *ABY*³ for training LR and LoR models. Over a dataset with a feature size of 784 and batch size of 128, training in Blaze gains about $4\times$ more throughput in the preprocessing phase for both LR and LoR. For the online phase, Blaze gains $145.35\times$ and $31.89\times$ throughput for LR and LoR respectively compared to *ABY*³. Shifting focus to *Falcon* [41], which is an end-to-end 3-party protocol for efficient private training and the inference of large ML models. By combining techniques from SecureNN and *ABY*³, Falcon constructs improved protocols for various private ML operations, such as convolutions, matrix multiplications, private comparison, ReLU, and its derivative, division, and batch normalization. Compared to other private training frameworks, Falcon is about $4.4\times$ faster than *ABY*³ and $6\times$ faster than SecureNN. Furthermore, Falcon achieves $2\times$ to $60\times$ less communication overhead than *ABY*³ and SecureNN. Similarly, *SWIFT* [53] relies on an efficient, malicious-secure 3PC framework, that works over rings (\mathbb{Z}_{2^ℓ} and \mathbb{Z}_{2^1}). SWIFT provides Guaranteed Output Delivery (GOD) in the honest majority setting. The protocols work in the preprocessing (offline-online) model. One highlight contribution is the dot product protocol that achieves communication cost independent of the input vector sizes. The authors benchmark their method using LoR (for training and inference), LeNet [54] and VGG16 [55] NNs (for inference). Authors compare LoR model's training in a 3-party setup with BLAZE, finding similar performance and improved security.

Adam in Private [56] addresses specific tasks within a 3-party setting and specializes in tasks such as integer division, exponentiation, inversion, and square root extraction within the context of DNNs. To demonstrate the proposed protocol's scalability, the authors perform measurements on DNNs architectures, such as a 3-layer fully-connected network introduced in SecureML, AlexNet and VGG16 on two datasets – MNIST and CIFAR10. The experiments are carried out in both LAN and WAN and the results are compared to Falcon. The implementation

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of the Adam optimization algorithm allows the framework to converge faster and requires fewer epochs compared to Falcon. In terms of training time, Adam in Private is $3.2\times$ to $6.7\times$ faster than Falcon for the 3-layer NN, about $12\times$ to $14\times$ faster for AlexNet and $46\times$ to $48\times$ faster for VGG16.

While the above works demonstrate a CPU-only implementation, there are a few works that explore GPU assisted computation within the standard 3-party setting such as *CryptGPU* [49] and *Piranha* [57]. *CryptGPU* operates, where all inputs are secretly shared among three non-colluding servers executing the protocol. It is built on top of PyTorch [58] and Crypten [59]. Experiments show, that the GPU-based protocol can have a $150\times$ speed up over the CPU-based protocol for a convolution operation and up to $10\times$ the speed up for non-linear operations. The increased efficiency of GPU implementations, enables the framework to privately train big networks such as LeNet, AlexNet [60], VGG16 over MNIST, CIFAR-10 and ImageNet datasets. Compared to Falcon, *CryptGPU* achieves $6\times$ to $36\times$ improvement for private training. Though showing great progress in terms of GPU adoption, *CryptGPU* is tailored for a specific MPC protocol and can only demonstrate full end-to-end training on simple networks such as AlexNet. To improve upon this, *Piranha* [57] proposed a more general GPU-based framework that can be used to implement other MPC protocols. *Piranha* consists of three layers: On the device layer, *Piranha* implements a data abstraction that manages vectorized GPU data and integer GPU kernels to support acceleration for integer-based computation needed for MPC protocols. *Piranha*'s protocol layer uses the device layer to implement functionality for different MPC protocols, namely SecureML (2-party) [37], Falcon (3-party) [41], and Fantastic Four (4-party) [61]. In the application protocol, *Piranha* provides typical privacy-preserving layers for NNs such as the linear and convolution layers, pooling operations, the ReLU activation function, and layer normalization. The MPC protocols implemented with *Piranha* exhibit $16\text{-}48\times$ training time speed up compared to their native CPU implementations. *Piranha* is also the first PPML framework capable of training a big NN such as VGG16 (with over 100 million parameters) over the CIFAR10 dataset in a short amount of time (less than a day and a half).

Four-party Computation: As we move forward, the ongoing evolution of 3-party MPC protocols not only enhances efficiency, security, and applicability in collaborative computations but also lays the foundation for exploring more complex scenarios. This progress is evident in recent developments within 4-party MPC protocols, where innovative solutions address diverse challenges in secure computation. For example: *Trident* [62] proposes a framework in the setting of 4-parties with at most one corrupt participant over the ring \mathbb{Z}_{2^ℓ} . The sharing protocols follow the offline-online phase paradigm and are used to construct a mixed-world framework between the binary, arithmetic and GC worlds. Compared to *ABY*³ [50] (for LR), training with *Trident* is $4.88\times$ to $251.84\times$ faster in LAN and $2\times$ to $2.83\times$ in WAN. For the LoR model, Tri-

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dent's improvements range from $5.95\times$ to $67.88\times$ in LAN and $2.71\times$ to $2.96\times$ in WAN. Training the NNs, Trident is from $3.56\times$ to $62\times$ faster in LAN, and $2.97\times$ to $3.56\times$ faster in WAN. Building on the foundation laid by Trident, *MPCLeague* [63] operates within a 4PC setting over the ring \mathbb{Z}_{2^ℓ} , ensuring support for an honest majority with at most one corrupted party. The framework combines arithmetic, boolean and garbled worlds with efficient end-to-end conversions between them. The efficiency of MPCLeague in private NN training is benchmarked using networks such as LeNet and VGG16. Compared to Trident [62] based on runtime, communication, and cost, MPCLeague offers better performance overall.

In the same year, Koti *et al.* introduced *Tetrad* [64], a 4-party setting designed to tolerate at most one active corruption over the ring \mathbb{Z}_{2^ℓ} . Tetrad proposes a mixed MPC protocol that supports robustness and fairness. Similar to MPCLeague, the authors of Tetrad compared their results with Trident considering training time, communication and monetary cost, as this captures the effect of the total runtime and communication of the parties. Experimental results show that Tetrad is 3-4 \times faster than Trident and achieves approximately 30% better results in terms of monetary cost. To obtain security against malicious parties, Dalskov *et al.*, proposed *Fantastic Four* [61], an actively secure 4-party protocol for corruption over a ring \mathbb{Z}_{2^k} . The protocol tolerates one active corruption and satisfies security with abort, however, it also provides GOD with some extensions. The protocol guarantees to identify a semi-corrupt pair and remove one party in the pair, then proceeds to an actively secure 3-party protocol with abort. If the 3PC protocol succeeds, then the output is produced, and the computation is finished. If the 3PC protocol also aborts, then the protocol knows that it removed an honest party and will abort the remaining party in the corrupt pair. It then proceeds to a passively secure 2-party protocol. The protocol is applied for training fully-connected NNs with 1-3 dense layers and a LoR model on the MNIST dataset. For the LoR model, *Fantastic Four* achieves $172.05\times$ faster training time than SWIFT in 4PC setting, and $84.24\times$ in 3PC setting.

To summarize, the choice among 2-party, 3-party and 4-party MPC depends on the specific requirements and characteristics of the collaboration at hand. The lower party like the 2-party MPC may be favored for simplicity and lower computational overhead, whereas the more intricate 4-party MPC offers advantages such as enhanced collaboration, security, and flexibility in situations involving more than two parties. Adding more parties may offer better security and efficiency, though it necessitates more servers, more communication overhead, more efforts to coordinate and increased complexities in the algorithms.

8.3 Analysis of MPC approaches

While considerable progress has been made regarding the efficiency of MPC protocols, some of the current approaches remain computationally expensive and do not scale well with the types

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of NNs typically used in modern ML systems. Another significant problem is the requirement for continuous data transfer between parties and for their continuous online availability.

In this section, we provide a more in-depth comparison and systematization of the MPC protocols summarized in [subsection 8.2](#). We discuss their strengths and weaknesses with the aim of outlining current challenges that need to be addressed. We look at the privacy and security guarantees provided by these protocols as well as the data type supported and the evaluation parameters. We also check whether the given MPC protocols provide an OSI (see [Table 10](#)).

GPU Utilization: GPUs are considered one of the most significant foundations for the resurgence of ML, because their parallel architecture is well-suited to dense matrix operations. Consequently, ML frameworks, such as TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Caffe allow GPU acceleration. As GPUs played an important role in the success of modern ML techniques, they also became essential for scalable PPML. However, in the literature, most of the works on PPML are CPU-based and only two works consider the GPU-based research for PPML [[49](#), [47](#)]. One thing to remember is that while choosing and designing PPML protocols for the GPU, one must carefully calibrate them for the architecture. Protocols like Yao's GC are less well suited for taking advantage of GPU parallelism compared to an SS-based protocol. Similarly, protocols that require extensive finite field arithmetic will incur more overhead on the GPU compared to the protocols that only rely on arithmetic modulo of a power of 2.

Security: Currently the fastest MPC protocols only provide security with abort. This means that a malicious service provider will cause the computation to abort without any output thus rendering the later appearance of the input provider irrelevant. Some MPC techniques provide fairness. Protocols providing security with abort or fairness will not suffice as in both cases an adversary can cause the protocol to abort, thus not producing the desired output for the user. This leads to denial of service and heavy economic losses for the service provider. Therefore, some SotA MPC approaches, as described in [Table 10](#) ensure robustness, guaranteeing that the correct output is produced, no matter how the adversary behaves.

Secure Machine Learning (SML): SML refers to preventing leakage of user information by protecting the process of ML. As can be seen in [Table 10](#), different ways are used to achieve SML. In paper [[37](#), [46](#), [47](#), [65](#)], the authors used two-party computation, in papers [[36](#), [50](#), [52](#), [41](#), [53](#), [49](#), [56](#)], the authors used three-party computation, while in papers [[62](#), [61](#), [63](#), [64](#)] the authors used four-party computation. In [Table 10](#), we also consider the input/output or model privacy that the above works aim to protect. As input privacy is the key feature of PPML, all the above works provide input privacy. However, only few works incorporate output and model privacy (broader and active area of research).

Adversarial Model (AM): AM defines the threats and adversary capabilities on a cryptographic

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protocol. It can be classified either based on the adversarial behavior or on the number of corruptions [13]. Based on their behavior, the adversaries are categorized into semi-honest and malicious. In a semi-honest setting, the adversary follows the protocol, but tries to glean additional information from the message. Most of the literature usually assumes a semi-honest adversary as mentioned in Table 11. Said adversary is limited in its offensive capabilities. This type of adversary model lowers the performance requirements. In malicious behavior, the adversary arbitrarily deviates from the protocol. This requires the adversary to either follow the protocol or do something completely different. The second one is based on the number of corruptions, which can be further classified into two categories: honest and dishonest majority. If N parties are taking part in MPC, then in honest majority at most $(\frac{N}{2} - 1)$ are allowed to be corrupt, ensuring that the number of honest parties is in the majority. Adversely, in dishonest majority parties are allowed to be corrupt only as high as $N - 1$.

Data Types: Any computable function can be securely evaluated in MPC using two types of secret sharing: Additive Secret Sharing (ASS) [24] and Boolean Secret Sharing (BSS) [66, 67]. In ASS, the data is additively shared between the parties. For example, D is the original dataset, which is then shared to two parties: one party has the share $D1$, while another party has the share $D2$. $D1$ and $D2$ can reconstruct D by adding their data together. Therefore, as long as they do not collude, the original dataset D is kept private. ASS uses an arithmetic circuit and supports efficient calculations over integers and floating-point, that do not involve comparisons. In these protocols, additions are cheap, whereas multiplications are expensive. Alternatively, in BSS the data is XORed shared between the parties (bit by bit). For BSS, the MPC uses boolean circuits and supports boolean points [67], as such they are well suited for comparison, division and multiplication operations. As mentioned in [68] to date, the majority of techniques (PPML) are implemented using integers, while there are undeniable limitations to integer arithmetic. In contrast, as can be seen in Table 10, the papers that we have surveyed for MPC mostly use boolean points.

8.4 Takeaways

Following the results of our work, we have observed the following key takeaways, which may instigate further research:

- **High computational and communication costs.** The main reason HE has not been adopted for standardized use is related to the high cost associated with model training. Since the amount of noise and the size of the ciphertext increase during mathematical operations on encrypted values, the training time required for an encrypted model increases almost exponentially with every processed batch. Consequently, though accuracy remains high enough to compare with plaintext models, the training time (while using HE), is multiple times longer

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Table 10 – Comparison among privacy-preserving training methods using MPC

Framework	Input/Output Model	GOD	Fairness	Abort	Integer	Boolean	Floating Point	Public Implementation	Private Implementation	Accuracy	Complexity	Communication	Time										
														Theoretical Metrics			Data types			Parameters for Comparison			
														Privacy	Security								
2PC	SecureML	●	-	-	-	✓	✓	●		✓	✓	✓	✓										
	Quotient	●	-	-	-	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	ParSecureML	●	-	-	-	✓	-	-	●	-	✓	✓	✓										
	ABY ²	●	-	-	-	✓	✓	-	●	-	✓	✓	✓										
	AriaNN	●	-	-	-	-	✓	-	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
3PC	SecureNN	●	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	ABY ³	●	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	-	✓	✓										
	BLAZE	●	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	-	●	✗	✓	✓	✗										
	Falcon	●	✗	✗	✓	✓	-	-	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	SWIFT	●	✓	✗	✗	-	✓	-	●	✗	✓	✓	✓										
	Adam in Private	●	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	CryptGPU	●	-	-	-	-	✗	✓	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	Piranha	●	-	-	-	-	-	-	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
4PC	Trident	●	✗	✓	✗	✗	-	-	●	✓	✓	✓	✓										
	Fantastic Four	●	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	-	●	✗	✓	✓	✓										
	MPCLeague	●	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	-	●	-	✓	✓	✓										
	Tetrad	●	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	●	✗	✓	✓	✓										

Table 11 – Comparison between privacy-preserving training methods using MPC

Framework	Year	Semi-honest Threat Model	Malicious Threat Model	Supported Layers				Techniques Used				LAN/WAN		Evaluation Dataset			Neural Network Architectures					
				Convolutional	ReLU	Maxpool	Linear	OT	GC	Secret Sharing	FSS	LAN	WAN	MNIST	CIFAR	Tiny ImageNet	ImageNet	From SecureML	From MiniCNN	LeNet	AlexNet	VGG16
				Theoretical Metrics				Techniques Used				LAN/WAN		Evaluation Dataset			Evaluation Metrics					
2PC	SecureML	2017	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Quotient	2019	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	ParSecureML	2020	●	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✗	-	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	ABY ²	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	AriaNN	2022	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	-	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
3PC	ABY ³	2018	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	SecureNN	2019	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
	BLAZE	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Falcon	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	SWIFT	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Adam in Private	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
	CryptGPU	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
4PC	Piranha	2022	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	●	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	Trident	2020	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Fantastic Four	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	●	✓	✗	✗	-	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	MPCLeague	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	-	✓	✗	●	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Tetrad	2021	●	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	●	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

than the plaintext counterpart.

Other contributions rely on MPC through distributed architectures, trading off the computational performance and communication overhead. MPC offers a significantly better level of security at the expense of costly cryptographic operations, leading to computational and communication cost increases. For example, in MPC each party has minimal computational costs. However communication between parties is required and this can cause increased communication costs. Both HE and MPC need to modify the model structure to match the correspond-

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ing PPML protocols. This affects accuracy and hinders efficiency with existing frameworks. One can see that HE and MPC have their own pros and cons in terms of security, effectiveness, efficiency and scalability. We believe that hybrid approaches to training and inference, such as the ones proposed by POSEIDON [39] can enjoy the benefits of each component, thus provisioning the optimal trade-off between ML task performance and privacy-preserving overhead.

- **Lack of open-source implementations.** While currently there is a gap between theoretical advances and real-world applications, there are certain open-source projects and tools dedicated to PPML [69, 70, 71]. OSI is the foundation of a lot of the modern scientific research – providing reliability, flexibility, transparency, and opportunities for collaboration. However, neither of the HE-based works provided OSI and that remains a prevalent issue in other work we did not delve into during this study [38, 72, 73]. Also, as shown in Table 10, 9 of the 17 works provide OSIs for MPC, while the remaining do not, however there are some other issues relating to protocol implementation, such as lack of proper documentation. Because of the sheer difficulty of the implementation task, most researchers only cover the results documented in the original paper, instead of recreating the implementations. This in turn causes problems, such as inability to reproduce the results of the papers and test the implementation in other environments or on different datasets. One of the main contributions of this overview is to highlight the importance of OSI in PPML and the need for reproducibility and usability considerations in research. We aim to bridge the gap by encouraging researchers and practitioners to prioritize open-source practices and share their implementations as this would provide:
 - Reproducibility and Progress: OSI provide opportunity to other researchers to reproduce and validate the results of a paper. By sharing the code, researchers contribute to the transparency and integrity of the scientific process, allowing others to verify and build upon their work. This leads to increased confidence and fosters a culture of reproducibility. Additionally, OSI facilitate collaboration and knowledge sharing. When codes are made public, other researchers can build upon the existing work, enhance it, and develop new techniques more rapidly. This accelerates the progress in the field of PPML by leveraging the collective efforts and expertise of the research community.
 - Long-term sustainability and wider impact: OSI are often maintained and supported by a community of contributors, ensuring their long-term sustainability. By encouraging researchers, to share their code, it promotes the continuous development, improvement, and maintenance of PPML implementations, thus addressing issues such as software bugs, compatibility with new platforms or libraries, and evolving security requirements, ensuring the longevity and usefulness of the implementations over time. Additionally, it lowers the barrier to entry for those interested in utilizing PPML for practical purposes.

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- **Lack of possible attack analysis on implementations.** Both proposed implementation of HE covered here assumes that the server is a semi-honest third-party and can only listen and watch the results of the training and inference without attempting to gain any additional information through malicious means. As mentioned previously, the assumption is realistic in most real-world scenarios involving the use of cloud-based server providers. It does, however, reveal a lack of analysis when it comes to potential ML attacks on the protocols. As a result, the lack of analysis on potential attacks points to a possible gap in the security of HE, when used in PPML. That is due to the fact that ML tasks open new vectors of attack for malicious actors. Similarly, most of the MPC protocols covered in this study consider the honest, but curious model, however, some studies also take the malicious model into account. While the works we investigated assume a non-colluding server, collusion between the parties must be taken into account in all of these adversary models. In MPC, collusion is unavoidable and poses a severe privacy concern, because it allows parties to learn each other's sensitive private input. Typically, parties in collusion share their data and function parameter settings with one another. Therefore, it is crucial to weight privacy against collusion, while creating an effective MPC protocol.
- **Lack of privacy-conscious regulatory frameworks** The available privacy-related regulations may require companies to announce that they are collecting all data and possibly provide users with the choice to opt out of said data gathering. However this appears to be a zero-sum game. Privacy policies can help data owners determine which data is shared, under what conditions, with whom, and for what purposes. It is essential to ascertain whether the policy will be implemented on the client or server side, which would change it into a format, where the data owner could allow or restrict access to other users and the server for certain purposes (such as marketing) or at least remove access users posing a possible privacy threat.

8.5 Challenges and Novel Approaches

Despite the aforementioned techniques for protecting private data, while performing ML training, non-privacy ML algorithms are still frequently employed, and private data is still transferred to the cloud. To date, there is no silver-bullet technique, when it comes to achieving privacy in ML. The privacy degree offered by the techniques we presented varies a lot depending on many factors such as the ML algorithm used, the adversary's capabilities and resources etc. Below we will discuss in detail the challenges of existing PPML techniques and their possible solutions.

While ML advancements are frequently offered, the PPML techniques covered in this document are linked to specific ML algorithms. Therefore, PPML techniques are required to cope with the most recent advancements in ML. This creates a challenge, where both HE and MPC need

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to modify the model structure to match the corresponding PPML protocols. This affects the training and inference accuracy and hinders compatibility with existing ML frameworks.

HE and MPC allow work on encrypted data, thereby preserving the utility of the original datasets. However, their domain is quite limited, and scalability can be a major issue due to high costs. Both methods have differing advantages and disadvantages and as can be seen in the covered papers, contributions, relying on MPC through distributed architectures, trade off lower computational costs with higher communication overhead. MPC offers a better level of security at the expense of costly networking operations, e.g., in MPC each party has less computational cost compared to HE but requires a lot of communication between parties. This can, lead to high communication costs. On the other hand, in HE, the server incurs a substantial computational cost, as it has to train the entire model on its own, at almost no communication cost, as all of the data needed for training is sent to the server once. A possible way to combat the high costs of both techniques and achieve a higher degree of privacy may require the combination of multiple PPML techniques. Recent literature has proposed combinations of FL with HE [39, 74], or DP with HE [75, 76] or MPC [77, 78], aiming for higher privacy guarantees and lower costs.

Following the analysis presented, we introduce a variety of solutions we have developed throughout the project which address some of the issues inherent in PPML. We delve into the full implementation of these schemes in other project related documents (such as Deliverable 1.1 and 2.1).

- DNN have millions of parameters. This is the main reason, why they are computationally expensive. Additionally, training a DNN on HE data increases the computing cost even more, sometimes to an unacceptable level. One possible approach for PPML is to use split learning (SL) [79], as it divides a DNN model so that part of the model is trained on the client side using plaintext data, and the remaining part is trained on the server side using encrypted data [80]. As part of the model is trained on plaintext, the DNN model's overall computation costs are lowered. Also, the privacy of user data is preserved as *a)* SL itself is believed to be a promising approach for raw data protection, and *b)* the computation on the server side is performed on top of encrypted data, hence not revealing information about client data.
- FL and SL have offered solutions to the privacy problems in ML, however, they are not complete and present various security problems and privacy leakages [81, 82, 83]. HE can be used to solve the privacy leakage in SL and FL.
- A great deal of work has recently been put into developing a reliable and secure protocol for ML tasks including MPC. In MPC, the parties constantly communicate to jointly compute a function, thus adding overhead. An alternative to MPC is to employ a hybrid strategy that combines SL and Function Secret Sharing (FSS) [84]. The model's initial layers are trained

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using SL on the client side, while its remaining layers are trained using FSS on the server side. Sending the data to the layers is all that is required to execute the layers on the client side. However, FSS is used to construct the secret shares, for each layer on the server.

These directions show immense promise for PPML as combining techniques allows us to make use of the benefits of both techniques (added security, novel ways of computation on encrypted data, etc.), all while reducing their possible drawbacks (i.e. high computational/communications overhead or existing privacy leakages). As such, we provide additional analysis of a PPML work using purely FSS [65] to act as a baseline for comparison when combining it with SL in Deliverable 2.1.

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8.6 Function Secret Sharing

Here we cover the underlying primitives used to construct functions within an FSS scheme from [Definition 7](#).

8.6.1 Primitives

Pseudo-random number generator. A PRNG is an algorithm that takes a short, random seed and produces a longer sequence of pseudo-random bits. In FSS, it is used to generate the keys for the FSS protocol. Each party starts with a random seed, and uses the PRNG to generate a sequence of keys. These keys are then used to generate CW for the FSS protocol.

Correction word. It is a special value used in FSS to correct the private shares being compared between two parties. The CW shifts a pseudo-random string so that it matches another random string on one side and remains independent on the other side. Each node in the binary decision tree generates its own CW, which is computed by applying a PRNG to the private shares being compared at that node. The resulting value is then used to correct the shares by computing an XOR operation on them with the CW. This ensures that the shares are equal if the input bits are the same, and different if the input bits are different. The CW is passed down to the child nodes of the current node in the binary decision tree, where it is used to correct the shares at those nodes as well. This process continues until the final output of the binary decision tree is computed.

Equality test. A test that involves comparing m_{pub} to a private value α and the goal is to determine whether m_{pub} is equal to α or not. The random mask α and the private input ATm are combined using modular arithmetic and published to obtain a public value m_{pub} . The equality test is performed using a binary decision tree of depth n , where n is the number of bits in the input m_{pub} . The tree evaluates the input using f_0, f_1 , which are generated using FSS. The path from the root to α is called the special path. The two servers (P_0, P_1) start from the root and update their state depending on the bit $m_{pub}[i]$ using a CW from f_0, f_1 . If $m_{pub}[i] == \alpha[i]$, they stay on the special path and output 1, otherwise, they output 0. The main idea is that the servers on the special path have specific states (s_0, t_0) and (s_1, t_1) , where s_0 and s_1 are independent and identically distributed and $t_0 \oplus t_1 = 1$ (see the dotted lines in [Figure 9](#)). When the servers are out of the special path, the CW ensures that $s_0 = s_1$ but remain random and indistinguishable, and $t_0 = t_1$, guaranteeing $t_0 \oplus t_1 = 0$. To reconstruct the result, each server outputs its value t_j , and the final result is obtained by $t_0 \oplus t_1$.

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Figure 9 – Function secret sharing for equality test

Comparison test. The comparison test involves a binary decision tree with a depth of n . In this test, the path from the root down to the greater value is called the special path. Each server starts at the root of the binary decision tree and updates their state based on the bits using CW from f_0 and f_1 . The goal is to evaluate all the paths simultaneously. When a server deviates from the special path, they either fall on the left side for $m_{pub} < \alpha$ or on the right side for $m_{pub} > \alpha$ (see Figure 10). Hence, at each node, an additional step is taken where a leaf label is output depending on the bit value $m_{pub}[i]$. The label is 1 only if $m_{pub}[i] < \alpha[i]$ and all previous bits are same. Only one label, either the final label (which corresponds to $m_{pub} = \alpha$) or the leaf label can be equal to 1, because only one path is taken. Therefore, the servers return the sum of all the labels to obtain the final output.

8.6.2 Performance Evaluation

Experimental setup For the experiments, we used a machine running Ubuntu 20.04 LTS, processor 12th generation Intel Core i7-12700, 32 GB RAM mesa Intel graphics (ADL-S GT1). We implemented our code using Python 3.7 and it is made available on GitHub³. FSS implemented using the PySyft framework⁴ and a modified version of AriaNN⁵. To get a more consistent and reproducible result, we ran our experiments a total of 10 times for each experiment, totaling 60 executions of the code with different settings. However, in our study, we are

³<https://github.com/UnoriginalOrigi/SplitFSS>

⁴<https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft/tree/ryffel/0.2.x-fix-training>

⁵<https://github.com/LaRiffle/ariann>

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Figure 10 – Function secret sharing for comparison test

reporting the top three results for each model (refer to Table 12). In the experiments we measured the communication costs, training times, and accuracy of the model after each epoch and report the total costs after full training. The communication costs are calculated by measuring the byte length of serialized objects sent through packets. Time measurements are taken by making use of the in-built *time* module from Python. The loss is calculated using mean squared error.

The model used in this study, consists of two Conv2D layers, two Max-pooling, four ReLUs and two Fully Connected layers. Among these layers, ReLU is supported as a direct application of the equality and comparison protocol, while the Conv2D layers are computed using beaver triples. In terms of hyperparameters, we train all networks with $E = 10$ epochs, $\eta = 0.002$ learning rate, $p = 0.9$ momentum, a batch size of $n = 128$, and the total training data samples $m = 59904$ (as the incomplete final batch is dropped).

FSS performance For our benchmarking we used AriaNN [65] – a promising solution for performing PPML on sensitive data. The authors have shown that AriaNN provides competitive performance compared to existing work, and have demonstrated its practicality by running private training on MNIST using models like LeNet. Given the promising outcomes achieved by AriaNN in comparison to other works, we adopted it as the base paper for our study.

In our experimentation, we replicated the results for AriaNN, which we refer to as the private local model. To thoroughly assess and compare the impact of FSS on performance, we initial-

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Table 12 – Performance comparison: training and testing results for various privacy-preserving models

Experimental Details		Training Statistics				Testing Statistics	
Dataset	FSS	Client Comm (MB)	Server Comm (MB)	Training Time (minutes)	Training Comm (MB)	Testing Comm (MB)	Testing Accuracy (%)
MNIST	✗	1931.85	1.65	1.44	1933.51	313.39	99.36
	✓	3861.32	3.57	1190.59	3864.90	1253.01	97.01
FMNIST	✗	1931.92	1.72	1.52	1933.65	313.40	89.88
	✓	3860.53	3.57	1814.74	3864.76	1253.01	74.44
CIFAR-10	✗	4760.91	1.43	1.21	4742.35	939.60	66.04
	✓	9479.76	2.97	2234.23	9583.29	3757.80	65.57

ized two models: one before applying FSS (referred to as the “public local model”) and one after applying FSS, both with the same set of initial weights. Our analysis, clearly indicates that the accuracy obtained before and after applying FSS remains nearly identical. In simpler terms, the implementation of FSS exhibits no noticeable effect on the performance of the models. As can be seen in [Table 12](#), the private local model achieves an impressive test accuracy of approximately 97.29%, closely followed by accuracies of 97.04% and 97.61%. This showcases that the private local model attains a commendable level of accuracy, lacking only by a modest 2% to 3% when compared to the public local models.

However, when we examine the training time for private local model over 10 epochs, a significant contrast emerges. Private local model necessitates approximately 1288 minutes, which is roughly $900\times$ more time-consuming than the training of the public local models. Additionally, the training communication cost incurred by private local model is $2\times$ higher, and the testing communication cost is $4\times$ greater compared to the public local models. The communication costs reported in [Table 12](#) do not take into account the preprocessing communication costs for transmitting the FSS keys and securely computing each function. The preprocessing costs for the private local model is 10.572851 MB per batch.

In conclusion, private local model demonstrates its potential as a promising solution for maintaining data privacy while achieving commendable accuracy in ML. Nonetheless, it is important to remember that using private local model comes with significant drawbacks in terms of the time it takes to train models and the extra communication needed. This should be carefully weighed when deciding if it is the right choice when selecting a privacy-preserving framework for specific use cases.

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9 Conclusion

In this deliverable, we provide an extension to the previous document on how HE and FE can be used to provide operations on encrypted data without losing accuracy or leaking privacy (aside from what is important for the functions itself). Firstly, we designed a multi-client verifiable FE scheme for inner products. While the emphasis in recent research has primarily been on functionality and performance, the importance of verifiability in FE is understudied. Satisfying the property of verifiable decryption in FE, is an important step towards assuming stronger threat models, by removing trust from, traditionally, fully trusted entities. Additionally, our construction's easy decryption procedure makes the overall scheme efficient.

Secondly, In the introduction, we identified two issues in the classical FE scenario. The first one, the problem of trust in an authority, was the central question and the motivation of our work. To address it, we developed a transciphering technique that takes advantage of the security provided by HE to ensure privacy in an untrusted environment. We showcase the validity of our approach by providing a formal definition of our construction, an analysis of its security, and a protocol supported by practical experiments. The second problem was the question of function privacy or how to ensure confidentiality of the functional request. The HE-FE transciphering technique we developed guarantees this feature naturally, without requiring additional computations or assumptions. This underlines the possibilities offered by the combination of HE and FE.

Lastly, we analysed currently existing literature for MPC-based solutions for performing PPML, a usecase intrinsically linked to the HARPOCRATES project. We also covered a novel paradigm emerging in MPC, named FSS, which can shed light on novel ideas for performing secure training and inference of ML models. In our analysis we covered the security aspects, utility and methods for applying MPC to PPML and we list takeaways gleamed from current literature.

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